

White-wooden-chair: The Discovery and Meaning of Interaction/experience

By

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in Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Degree of Master of Arts,
Master of Arts (Visual Art & Design)

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work in this thesis is my own except for quotations and summaries which have been duly acknowledged.

16 June 2011

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White-wooden-chair: The Discovery and Meaning of Interaction/experience

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to

Ah-kong (my grandfather) – Teoh Chan Seng

who sowed the “seed” on this soul.

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I would like to thanks:

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my parent who created this soul.

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ABSTRACT

This thesis is the archive of the making and research of *White-wooden-chair*, project for the subject of *VSE 506 Graduate Thesis and Exhibition*, as part of the fulfilment for the completion of Master of Arts (Visual Art & Design), mixed mode degree programme.

This thesis contains seven chapters, which discuss:

1. The visual autobiography of *White-wooden-chair*.
2. Improvement of art making methodology – *Defragmentation of “Big Apple”*
Argument through the adaptation of few theories from Jacque Derrida’s *Deconstruction*, Hasnul Jamal Saidon’s *Southeast Asia Design Principles*, Fauzan Omar’s *Expanded Painting*, Niranjana Rajah’s *The End of Geography* argument and Roopesh Sitharan’s *Ethos of Post Colonialism*.
3. Pondering into David A. Kolb’s *Experiential Learning Theory*, James E. Zull’s *The Art of Changing the Brain* and *Chakra* Theory to further develops co-invented *Visual Sampling Method (VSM)* with Assoc. Prof. Hasnul Jamal Saidon, as alternative visual analysis method, under Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah, USM. And developing of *Cycle of Art Making* based on above materials as well.
4. Searching the meaning of Interaction/experience from varied perspectives, partly it is the journey into the endeavour and making of Information Art.

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Chapter 1: Seed of *White-wooden-chair* (Intention)

(By this definition, the artist has a new thought and idea to produce a piece of work. It also refers to the artist starting with the fundamental actions of his thought and expression. The artist responds immediately to this discovery through sketches, photo-documentation, collecting object or materials, and others preliminary actions that were triggered by his very first thoughts of art making. I have implemented “Cycle of Art Making” in this thesis writing for the sake of experiment. *Chapter 1: Seed of White-wooden-chair* describes the very beginning of the idea of *White-wooden-chair*.)

1.1 Ah-kong’s teaching

Throughout the making of *The Returning – Silent Dialogue* or *White-wooden-chair* (Ting Chuang, *The Returning - Silent Dialogue* 2010-2011), I was reminded of my late grandfather (Ah-Kong) who taught me how to write the Chinese character “四” (pronounced as “si”) when I was six years old. It is just a simple character - four, but it meant a lot to me. Ah-Kong said to write the character well, as anyone acquainted with the Chinese calligraphy will attest; one should learn the stroke order (笔顺) (Wikipedia 2011) first. Therein lays the analogy of the conduct of a gentleman. Formalistically, the character has four sides which form a rectangle; it looks like a house compound surrounded of four brick walls. The component “儿” (a child) is then placed inside the “house compound”. Ah-Kong joked that I better make sure everyone had returned home before I closed the door; which explains the writing order of character “四”. The character fall under “enclosures before contents” category where the outside enclosure is written before the content; then it is completed with the bottom stroke which is written last.

Conceptually the form of “四” depicts the notion of stability; it reflects the behaviour of gentleman (君子“四”平八穩) – who is the leader of family, the husband of the wife, the father of the children and a gentleman in the society. It underpins the stability of the universe as well as subtly points to the four directions in physical dimension; east, west, north and south. Ah-Kong reminded me that: 君子道者三，我無能焉：仁者不憂，知者不惑，勇者

不懼。《论语》第十四章 宪问篇 (The way of the “gentleman” is threefold. Virtuous, he is free from anxieties; wise, he is free from perplexities; bold, he is free from fear. In ‘The Analects’ Chapter XIV Constitutional Question Papers) (ielts.com 2010) Confucius suggested that; a gentleman treats others with tolerance, is kind-hearted, calm and unperturbed by any challenges from the universe; encapsulating the meaning of benevolence (仁) as a whole. Secondly, a gentleman should equip himself with wisdom and knowledge (知); to make him wise; encourage the significant of the state of being conscious, possess the ability to deal with all problems in physical environ that he resides. Lastly a gentleman should always speak the truth, be spontaneous in his response to his surroundings; and manifest the quality of “bravery” and ‘boldness’ (勇).

In order to contemporaries the notion of behaviour of “gentleman” (Confucius’s teaching) instead of the virtue of individual (man and woman) in the adaptation of globalisation phenomenon.

I was inspired by Ah-kong’s teaching; he seemed to infer that every existence has its mean and reason to be. Therefore we reap what we sow, as in Chinese saying, 种瓜得瓜, 种豆得豆。明·施耐庵《水浒传》第四十五回 (if a man plants melons he will reap melons; if he sows beans, he will reap beans) It also reflects Lao Zi’s (老子) Taoism (道) teaching, which celebrates the laws of complementary (对立转化) and the law of circulation (循环运动) in our dairy life. Even though the law of complementary contains two different components and forces; in others words Ying and Yang, man and women, east and west, and etc. Lao Zi believed that is the symbiosis of the two sides. (陈鼓应 2003) It is akin to the process of photosynthesis, flora needs carbon dioxides which are exhalant by fauna, and fauna inhaled fresh oxygen released by flora. Photosynthesis shows the transformation of air

molecular structures in micro level. On the other hand, in macro level the process demonstrates the circle of natural life in ecology.

As fetuses, we were inside our mother's womb for nine months. Then we were born – as babies, being cared for by our parents. We become children before growing up as individuals, having our own minds and personalities, meeting our soul mates, getting married and giving birth (women); to pass the torch on to the next generation. We get old and then leave the world to our children to continue the legacy; thus the cycle of life begins afresh. As Lao Zi manifested in chapter 42, “道”生一， 一生二， 二生三， 三生万物。万物负阴而抱阳，冲气以为和。(The Tao gave birth to the One. The One gave birth to Two and to Three; as a natural phenomenon to gave birth to all of creations. All things carry the Yin yet embrace the Yang, and with the complementariness of both; blend their life breaths as one to produce harmony.) Every existence has its meaning and reason to be; all life celebrates the unity of all creations.

The law of circulation describes the notion of beginning and returning. Ah-Kong, my grandfather, sowed the “seed” (thought) in me through his teachings. Who I am today is the “half growing fruit” (being) that Ah-Kong has cultivated. Ah-Kong's teachings are full of metaphors about the complexity of the circle of life; as I can visualise, like the interaction of multiple layers of circles which creates trans-relationship between each others. A circle calibrates years, months, weeks, days, hours, minutes, seconds and even fractions of a second; and the planted “seed” travels across time to manifest itself as the “half grown fruit” who are re-manifesting the “seed” to you. (While you are reading the texts)

One might ask, what are the lessons to be learned from Ah-kong's teaching and the making of *White-wooden-chair*?

It is simply a flashback of old but unforgotten days of a six year old kid sitting on the chair while Ah-kong was teaching him how to write character “四”. The *White-Wooden-Chair*, being a silent partaker of the ‘sowing’ process was once being “enlightened” as well; it is a part of the legacy, and a beneficiary of the cycle of life in Ah-Kong 80 years. *White-wooden-chair* is a re-manifestation of the “seed” as well.

1.2 [.my] *Life Is Empty* (2006)

In Jacques Derrida argument of circle of the abyss, which is explained the trans-relationship of artist and artwork (as two different entities); the intersection of both circles to form another “circle”; even though the interrelation of the “circle” and outside the “circle” form another “circle” of it; the complexity of “circles between circles” the question posted in Derrida’s essay entitled, *The Truth in Painting – Parergon i. Lemmata*, “Why a circle?”. Derrida suggested the abyss is in the middle of circle, and we set “ours” radius within the circle between circle. It reconstructs the existing surrounding form a neutral and open-ended ground, promotes highly adaptability and modularity for other potential making. (Derrida 2007) Derrida’s argument describes the trans-relationship between the lessons of writing character “四”, Ah-kong’s teaching, the Analects, Taoism, argument of circle of life, the “seed” and “half grown fruit”, *circle and the abyss*, and *White-wooden-chair*; entangles the thought behind the seed of *White-wooden-chair*. Perhaps it can arrange in other way; *White-wooden-chair*, *circle and the abyss*, the “seed” and “half grown fruit”, argument of circle of life, Taoism, the Analects, Ah-kong’s teaching and the lessons of writing character “四”.

The Influence Series (2006)

It all began on the moment of;

Dot has appeared and created lines on canvas.

Meanwhile lines have created shapes; then created form.

The variant arrangement of forms created dimension.

Where the duplication of dimension has occurred; consequently spatiality has created.

If those 3-dimensional spaces interconnected to each other, into 4th dimensional,

It touched my emotional sensitivity.

It is going to end one day when,

The canvas contains heavy capacity of visual elements.

Breathing spaces on canvas are limited meanwhile,

It lack of white spaces for visualisation where;

We can't feel those forms, we can't see those lines and,

We can't notice a single dot.

I remain as myself.

I experienced a major transformation in art making after recovering from the pain of terminating a relationship with my girlfriend of seven years. In 2006 I produced an assemblage work entitled *[.my] Life Is Empty* (MLIE) (Ting Chuang, *[.my] Life Is Empty* 2006) (Figure 1). It was the manifestation of the angst and paradoxical nature of love that I felt at that time. MLIE depicted my perception of “life”. The breakup triggered me to search for the meaning of relationships and the inter-reaction between humans. I blamed myself for the failure in that relationship and considered its failure as a retribution for my shortcomings.

Formalistically, it is a painted white bag containing several readymade objects; which depict the meaning of life. MLIE invites audience participation to take those objects from the

bag and return it after observing. The act of “taking and returning” – the physical interaction in itself is symbolical of the circle of life. After many years, in hindsight; I realised that the making of MLIE was the channel through which I heal myself and made my recovery; a metaphor of the rejuvenation in the cycle of life. The short statements excerpted from [.my] Life Is Empty (2006) is a reflection of that very process that I went through.

Figure 1 [.my] *Life Is Empty* (2006)

Grab an object from the white empty bag; return into the empty bag.

Drowning in nicotine; only dust left.

Staying for thousand years; only toxic left.

Addicted to sugar; only ants left.

Getting poisoned; only drug left.

Play-no-fun; only condoms left.

You drunk you drug; only bottles left.

Paying too much? Only empty hand left

“Clicking” make trouble. Finally, nothing is left over.

Life is still empty!

After my girlfriend left me,

reading Tristan Tzara’s “Lecture on Dada” (1922);

(Tristan Tzara, Robert Motherwell (Translated) 1922)

I was inspired and “cloned” a brand new “TC Liew” for the replacement...

[.my] *Life Is Empty* (2006) is the beginning of my art journey and the other works from the series of *Tan-jong i-tou bi-kin* (Made in Penang) (2006-2008) is also consider as the seed of *White-wooden-chair*; such as *Dare-to-open* (Ting Chuang, Dare-to-open 2006), *Meditation Framework: Mindset Building* (Ting Chuang, Meditation Framework: Mindset Building 2007), *Pot Luck* (Ting Chuang, Pot Luck 2007), *Ma-li pes-sta a-ri a-ri (Every day we visit the carnival)* (Ting Chuang, Ma-li pes-sta a-ri a-ri 2007), *The More We Get Together* (Ting Chuang, The More We Get Together 2008) and *Welcome Home* (Ting Chuang, Welcome Home 2008). Most of the works are interactive in nature; invite audience’ participations without digital aids. As shown in my final undergraduate project in which I

coined the term “passive interactivity”. It leads me to discover the meaning of interactivity while “passive” is referred to set of non-automatic yet touchable and playable gadgets (artworks); “interactivity” is explained the participation of audiences. White-wooden-chair extended the journey of that searching; for the meaning of interactivity through public installations.

“Art, in its form, unites the very same relation of doing and under-going, outgoing and incoming energy that makes an experience to be an ‘*experience*’ ”, quoted from *Art as Experience* by John Dewey. (Dewey 1934, 2007)

One might ask, what is the ‘*experience*’?

The ‘*experience*’ refers to; “The simulacrum is never that which conceals the truth — it is the truth which conceals that there is none. The simulacrum is ‘true’. —*Ecclesiastes*- (originally from Hebrew Bible)”, quoted from *Simulacra and Simulations - Jean Baudrillard (Selected Writings)*, edited by Mark Poster. (Jean Baudrillard, Mark Poster (edited) 2011)

One might ask, what is the ‘truth’?

The ‘truth’ refers to; “Simulacra¹ that are productive, productivist, founded on energy, force, its materialization by the machine and in the whole system of production; ‘simulacra of simulation’, founded on information, the model, the cybernetic game - total operationality, hyperreality, aim of total control.”, quoted from *Simulacra and Simulations – XIII, Simulacra and Science Fiction* by Jean Baudrillard, translated by Sheila Faria Glaser. (Jean Baudrillard, Sheila Faria Glaser (translated) 2011)

One might ask, what is the ‘simulacra of simulation’?

Simply suggests the notion of ‘interactivity’.

Figure 2 *Welcome Home* (2008), Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah's collection.

ⁱ *Simulacra and Simulation* identifies three types of simulacra and identifies each with a historical period:

First order, associated with the premodern period, where the image is clearly an artificial placemaker for the real item. The uniqueness of objects and situations marks them as irreproducibly real and signification obviously gropes towards this reality. Second order, associated with the modernity of the Industrial Revolution, where distinctions between image and reality break down due to the proliferation of mass-reproducible copies of items, turning them into commodities. The commodity's ability to imitate reality threatens to replace the original version, especially when the individual person is only concerned with consuming for some utility a functional facsimile. Third order, associated with the postmodernity, where the simulacrum precedes the original and the distinction between reality and representation vanishes. There is only the simulacrum, and originality becomes a totally meaningless concept.

(Quoted from: *Simulacra and Simulation*, From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia.)

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Chapter 2: Growing of *White-wooden-chair* (Imitation)

(This chapter addresses the “imitation” from my past experiences, as I treat it as an awakening signal in my life. This chapter partly adopted from research paper, co-written with Muhammad Hanif bin Hosainel Majidi entitled, *Meeting the South: Dialogues-through-drawings (2009): Generating Behaviourist Data through Drawings*, presented in *The 2nd Performing Arts as Creative Industries in Asia (PACIA) 2011 – Convergence in Performing & Creative Arts*, School of The Arts, Universiti Sains Malaysia.)

2.1 Encountering the move

Taking off from the notion of “the circle and the abyss” (Derrida 2007) as described by Derrida in the making of art, an artwork and, by extension the artist himself, should leave the “form”, lace it with “meditations” and further add interlacing of “cultural influence”. This process has been true in describing the growing of my project: *White-wooden-chair* (Ting Chuang, *The Returning - Silent Dialogue* 2010). It was metaphor of my life experiences; symbolises my circle of life, pointing to the journey that I have walked through and will continue to take. In 2009, I produced a series of artworks entitled *Meeting the South* (MTS) (2009)ⁱ in Johor Bharu. MTS unveiled my attitude and behaviour and through that engagement, built up the conceptual framework of my art making. Thus we can say that the seed of *White-wooden-chair* was grown in the making of *Meeting the South*.

The “growing” began, from a set of installation entitled *Let the North meets South* (2009)ⁱⁱ (林金兰 2009) (Ting Chuang, *Don't Worry It Just T-shirt series* 2009) which was exhibited at the Iskandar Malaysia Contemporary Art Show 2009 (IMCAS). Subsequently, I was invited to join IMCAS's Artist in Residence (AiR) 3-month programme, which I accepted and participated in. The installation narrates how people in the Northern region of Malaysia were living their lives after the *308 Political Tsunami* (Kit Siang 2009) while the Southern region was facing the Tebrau-Singapore Strait tensionⁱⁱⁱ. (Cornelius-Takahama 2000) (BBC 2006) (Ming 2010) (Wikipedia 2011) (Britannica 2011)

Coming from Penang, I am considered as an ‘outsider’ who stepped into the Southern region, commonly referred to as ‘the gate into the modernised city’. ‘Gate to the modernized city’ refers to Johor Baharu (JB), the main city of the State of Johor. I was understandably filled with a lot of curiosity because it was my very first trip to the South. People from the northern part of Malaysia typically stereotyped JB as the gateway for *Malaysian Singapore Permanent Residence* (PR) applicants, a base for Malaysians to earn Singapore Dollars, and a habitat for loan-shark debtors. The physical environment of JB does not excite me; but the modernised culture and people behind this ‘concrete jungle’ triggered my curiosity – what is JB?

The acceptance of IMCAS’s AiR programme outlines the journey of my transition; getting plugged into the national art scene, and relocating geographically to the Southern region of the Peninsular of Malaysia. IMCAS provided a 60 feet x 20 feet shop lot at the 4th floor of Danga City Mall, with glass wall frontage and door. Working inside the exposed shop lot made me felt ‘naked’ in public; one might say, it looked like *an artist working in a glass aquarium*. Visitors were viewing from the outside while I was working inside. It was not the best of arrangements and it was not very comfortable. I needed room to breathe.

A few questions then arise. How to engage the community in collaborative projects within a preset attitude and understanding of art making? It might be possible to do so in a limited and cautious way with the JB community; where the layman believes that art making is a God-given talent, only for the few ‘anointed’ ones. I decided to conduct an audience-participant project which employed drawings as a mediator to collect visual data through mark-making and as ‘props’. A site-specific installation is required to build up the mood and environment, as a ‘stage’ for public performance; in which I perform as ‘the artist’ and the participants as the ‘local community’. The third-person/participant’s friends witness the

‘performance art’ which take place inside the glass wall partition room. The setting sets the framework for the depiction of the concept of ‘meeting the south’.

By default, performance art should be documented by video or even still photographs. Usually a piece of performance art runs for a short duration and is located at the centre of the crowd. Due to technicalities and contingent difficulties however, the IMCAS management discouraged the project. Ideally *Meeting the South* (MTS) was the core platform to catalyse, generate, inspire, multiply, modularise and expand the idea of ‘north meet south’ into the making of a body of artwork. The framework drew from various sources; *Deconstruction (The Circle and The Abyss)* (Derrida 2007), adaptive and modular quality of *Southeast Asia Design Principles* (SADP) (Hasnul Jamal, Cabaran Praktis Seni Elektronik dalam Era Maklumat 2003) (Hasnul Jamal, Takung 2006), ideas of *Expanded Paintings* (Fauzan, Catan Lanjutan: Perluasan Bahan, Media dan Integrasi Makna dalam Seni oleh Pelajar-pelajar Seni Halus 2007), concepts of *The End of Geography* (Niranjan 2008) and arguments of *Ethos of Post Colonialism*. (Roopesh 2008) Therefore the conceptual framework is highly adaptive and modular like a water ripple, when it interfaces with other forces it multiply and creates more complex patterns.

2.2 Defragmentation the “Big Apple”

Below are the reasons of adaptation selected seminal manuscripts from local writers and researchers.

2.2.1 Derrida introduced a complex and adaptable approach to dismantle our “surrounding” through the reading of binary opposition – the signifier and “signified” (culture and linguistic studies); provides a “theory” (grammatology) and method (deconstruction)

of montage in any mode of writing. (Ulmer 1998). I have adapted the working strategy in visual manipulation. As I imagine it, an apple transforms itself into cluster of patches, like a piece of concept map which is holding layers of databases. It is a platform to structuralise complex information into organised systems, promoting different potential reading. It de-centralises the influence of the master narrative from a single domain.

2.2.2 Hasnul generalised and contextualised eastern design patterns which adapted Daoism, Sufism and ICT as its fundamentals, and further discussed the trans-relationship between art and science, coined as Southeast Asia Design Principles (SADP). Potentially it multiplies the reading of “circle of the abyss” to achieve intertextuality, as the principles suggested by Hasnul; modularity, diversity of disciplines, interconnectedness and inter-locking, multiple centres (non-linear), flexibility, audience-oriented and inter-activity. Hasnul experimented SADP in *Takung* (container) (2005), which was his milestone of curatorial development. He wrote, “We are the containers and the contained, intertwined in a reservoir of love, far larger and finer than what we can imagine with the aid of our naked perception.” (Hasnul Jamal, *Takung* 2006) If Derrida’s approach is able to transform a single apple into set of database therefore those set of databases should interlace to become molecule-like structures of multilayered information. The “fragmented-apple” becomes a set of modular architecture of “fragmented-apples”; meaning it does not look like an apple but just tiny patches of databases about an “apple”.

2.2.3 Fauzan is well known of his *Layers Series* (Fauzan, Layer Series 1982) since his return from MFA studies in early eighties. More precisely Fauzan explored the

reading of materials contextually and technically and this is always postulated as “de-materialise” by him. Artists are seeking for new mediums, exploiting cutting edge technology in order to widen the possibility of expression and creation of marks, as exemplified in the making of *Expanded Painting*. (Fauzan, Catan Lanjutan: Perluasan Bahan, Media dan Integrasi Makna dalam Seni oleh Pelajar-pelajar Seni Halus 2007) It encourages varied reading of subjects, based on different factors from the surroundings such as cultural adaptation, social influence, technological advancement and individual reasons. Besides “its” formalistically importance, the notion of *Expanded Painting* promotes the importance of individual voices. Subscribing to Fauzan’s argument, the “fragmented-apples” transform into varied architecture settings which contain measurable and spontaneous patterns of information.

2.2.4 Based on Niranjan’s argument on the other hand, the “fragmented-apples” become an abundance of databases which does not hold tangible structure. Besides it can also be described as an illusion of projected “apple” in the virtual and lucid environment of information. In his essay entitled “*Beyond the Site: Installation Art at the End of Geography*”, Niranjan shared that he is seeking for the possibility of expanding the reading and practice of art making in the virtual environment. In an effort to develop new art language in virtual reality he moves into making web art. His work; “*The End of Geography*” is a metaphor of diverse ways fine art adapt itself to the shift and tilt of the information age.

2.2.5 Reading Roopesh’s “*Ethos of Post Colonialism*” I am inspired to ponder about questions of self, identity, moving and relocations in the midst of globalisation. Roopesh’s arguments inspire me to think of how to unveil and remind me of the

“seed” of Ah-Kong’s teachings. Subscribing to Roopesh’s argument I picture the “pineapple” as an answer to the “fragmented-apples”, a metaphor the localisation of western framework in local context.

Figure 3 show the visualisation of selected arguments

Figure 3 above outlines the differences between suggested arguments even though it derives from single intention, which is expanding and exploring the existing knowledge. One might ask, what if there are others way of visualisation? This leads to the question simply demonstrated as diversity and modularity quality of the framework below:

Choose a local fruit which synonymous to "big apple" based on your preferences?

- Option:*
- (a) mango*
 - (b) rambutan*
 - (c) watermelon*
 - (d) pineapple*
 - (e) durian*
 - (f) nutmeg*
 - (g) other local fruits (specify)*

If the framework is described as a 'tool'; conceptually it functions as a device, a platform, a studio and an environment for art making. In academic terms, this usually refers to studio-based research methodology (practice-based or other ways of phrasing). The concept of 'methodology' refers to the attitude and behaviour of making. In their manifesto *Toward Mystical Reality* (1974) Piyadasa and Suleiman, argued that the artist's behaviourist practices are a form of meditation for those who believe in Zen practices or Minimalism approach in western terminology; which they referred to as an "event". In response, Salleh bin Joned writing in *Open Letter for Piyadasa* (1975) further discussed the adaptation of Zen in art practice and with his "Zen-pissing" dismantled both the artists' arguments. Roopesh holds the view that they rejected the materialistic reading of an object and returned to the eastern perspective of reality. They wrote that: 'the serious Asian modernists have been left

with little choice but to lean heavily on a modern art tradition that has its origin in the western scientific and intellectual climate' (Redza Piyadasa, Suleiman Esa 1974) (Salleh 2010) (Roopesh 2008) (Hasnul Jamal Saidon & Liew Ting Chuang 2010). The framework provides conceptual space for me to 'de-materialise' the physical environment that I was in; the glass aquarium studio, the visit of local community, the witness of the third-person and others; to build "firewall" for securing the frequency within my aura zone.

The framework also 'de-materialised' the collected drawings from participants into the form of 'codes'. It can be interpreted as the participants' response to the glass aquarium studio (the ambience). The way participants responded to the pre-printed stylised self-portrait (sitting and meditating posture) referred to as their perceptions - the rationale of participants - were making marks in unique approaches. These 'codes' conceptually represented a set of 'information' about the participants such as their expressions, behaviours, ideas and thoughts; which were then converted into another form of interpretation. It created a 'neutral ground' for other curators, artists and researchers to interpret the 'codes' in varied readings. Those 'codes' are evidence for others to make decisions, create meanings and witness the complex processes of the human mind in an effort to understand the lucidity and fluidity of space. (Jensen 1986)

Figure 4: *White-wooden-chair's* conceptual framework.

2.3 The meaning of “chair”

Beside its conceptual framework, the growing of *White-wooden-chair* can be traced chronologically from the creation of my artworks. Most of my artworks use used objects, collected junks and ready-mades that are easily collected and found. Looking back, the appearance and the depictions of “chair” have been presented in many ways in my past works. The manipulations of the conceptualization of “chair” began in the transition between *Tan-jong i-tuo bi-kin (made in Penang)* (2006-2008) and *Meeting the South* (2009) series. Selected artworks which adopted the images of “chair” are listed in chronological order as below:

2.3.1 *Welcome Home* (Ting Chuang, Welcome Home 2008) (Figure 2)

Welcome Home ironically depicts the loneliness of old folks who are/were waiting for the return of their grown-up children. Most of the children have their own family; and live apart from their ancestral home. The hand-painted, monochromatic, distorted life size photograph figures are/were my late grandfather (Ah-Kong) and grandmother (Ah-Mah); she is staying with my second elder uncle. The distorted images of my grandparents were captured through the eyes of a six-year-old; looking from a knee-high perspective of approximately three feet.

One of the wooden antique chairs which were presented by Ah-Kong is attached to the printed canvas. The attached chair extended the illusory space in between Ah-Kong printed figure; simulating the illusion of Ah-Kong holding the attached chair outwards, inviting the audience to sit on it. It is a gentle reminder to the audience to visit their parents always, who are waiting for their return before it is too late. On a personal level, the making of *Welcome Home* was the healing of my loss of my late Ah-Kong. I have given meaning to the chair appropriating it as an agent to accompany and remind me about love and the family. *Welcome Home* (2008) is a tribute to Ah-Kong, my late grandfather.

2.3.2 *The More We Get Together* (Ting Chuang, The More We Get Together 2008)

The More We Get Together celebrates the togetherness of multiracial society. Realistic thumbnail portraits images (street old folks) painted on wooden sphere puzzle I named as *Interconnection Puzzle* (团结谜). It has six components, each of the components have two different portraits painted separately. Members of the audiences are invited to solve

the puzzle. Unfortunately the puzzle could not be solved because one of the components is intentionally dissimilar to the others. Therefore *Interconnection Puzzle* paradoxically remind us to celebrate unity and cooperation among the various races in society, toward the truly *Malaysia^{iv}* vision (perhaps dream).

Figure 5: *The More We Get Together* (2008), Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah's collection.

Although none of “chair” images had been manipulated in *The More We Get Together* but through the participation of audiences, the notion of chair is translated as “seat”. Simply the audience is asked to sit down and play. It encourages audiences to feel, interact and enjoy the designed puzzle. Consequently, the member of audiences learns about “interconnectivity” through the game. In *The More We Get Together* (2008), the hidden chair/seat symbolises harmony in multiracial society.

2.3.3 *Don't Worry It Just T-shirt series* (Ting Chuang, *Don't Worry It Just T-shirt series* 2009)

Figure 6: *Don't Worry It Just T-shirt series* (2009), Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah's collection.

Don't Worry It Just T-shirt depicts the social impact of political change, where Pakatan Rakyat (People's Alliance) rules northern region of Peninsular Malaysia. During that time, political issues became Penangites' soap opera. On the other hand, mainstream media reported gossips on politicians. Therefore I translated the highlighted news-clippings into illustrations, painted on readymade t-shirts. I re-painted on printed Penang landscape images. Each of images has its own voice, hung on the chair shoulders; as a metaphor of being

responsible of the happening, as in Chinese saying, 肩负 (literally translated as shoulder).

The installation semantically demonstrated the hidden narrative. In *Don't Worry It Just T-shirt*, the chairs represented different “persons” which show the different “characteristics” on their own; based on the load on its “shoulders” – the shoulders of chairs/responsibilities.

2.3.4 Artist-In-Aquarium (Ting Chuang, Artist-In-Aquarium 2009)

Figure 7: *Artist-In-Aquarium* (2009), photography documented due to site-specific setting, credited to Chew Winwin. Shared copyright by IMCAS 2009 and the artist.

Artist-In-Aquarium simulated my experiences in aquarium-like studio during the artist-in-resident programme; where the setting translated the experience to the audiences through simulacrum approaches. The audiences are invited to physically interact with the setting and to walk around the designated interior space. In *Artist-In-Aquarium*, the notions of chairs were described as power and ownership between individual and authority. It played certain specified roles in the designed installation.

The site-specific installation is required to build up the mood and environment, as a 'stage' for public performance; whereby the 1st person audience was performing as 'the artist' and the 2nd audience was performing as the 'local community'. The 3rd audience witnessed the 'performance art' which was happening inside the room. The setting enhanced the depiction of the concept of 'meeting the south'.

2.3.5 *After Fauzan & Hasnul, What's Next?* (Ting Chuang, *After Fauzan & Hasnul, What's Next?* 2009)

In *After Fauzan & Hasnul, What's Next?* is enquiring the impact and consequence in the local art scene after the significant pioneering efforts of Fauzan and Hasnul; namely "expanded painting" and "electronic art". Their involvement leads to new trajectories in local art scene since the eighties by Fauzan; and the nineties by Hasnul. These new trajectories are quickly taken up and widely practiced by the contemporary generation; their efforts grabbed the attentions of international practitioners, art institutions and art collectors. Fauzan and Hasnul' endeavours can be seen as big leap from the 70's *New Scene* from one to another; from the teacher to the student; from the traditional medium to the electronic medium. The question that needs to be asked is: What is the next jump after these two "giants" in the art

scene? I am sharing the awareness to my contemporary peers about the importance of change where a “new leader” is needed after the nineties.

Figure 8: After Fauzan And Hasnul, *What's Next?* (2009)

A painted left-hand glove and a painted Yo-yo hang above an arm chair; inviting the audience to sit and wear the glove. The top side of glove depicts imitations of Fauzan’s *Layer Series* (Fauzan, *Layer Series* 1982) and the bottom side imitates Hasnul’s *Ong* (Hasnul Jamal, *Ong* 1997), tied to the Yo-yo; which painted self portrait (side profile) on both side of the Yo-yo. The arm chair illustrate the hidden power and authority in the local art scene which is growing in certain patterns; monotonous, influential art buying pattern; being popularised and “fashioned” art style pattern; and institutionalised thought patterns of art in most of the higher institutions of art. (Suzieana 2008) (Roopesh, *Ethos of Post Colonialism* 2008) (Hasnul Jamal, *Under-deconstruction: Contemporary Art in Malaysia after 1990* 2008)

Members of the audiences are invited to perceive the simulation of being a “capitalist” who is able to control the printed glove to the right and left.

2.3.6 *I Love You, Hug Me!* (Ting Chuang, *I Love You, Hug Me!* 2009)

Figure 9: *I Love You, Hug Me!* (2009)

Obviously chair is the dominant part of *I Love You, Hug Me!* This chair symbolises the power of authority where the mortified “teddy bear” have been locked to the white chair.

Even though the “teddy bear” is unable to open its mouth, it demonstrated “it” is able to express with certain censorship; a land of “dry” interconnectivity and lack of love.

2.3.7 Re-visiting “Ah Kong” In Memories (Ting Chuang, Re-visiting "Ah Kong" in Memories 2008 - 2009)

Figure 10: Photo documentation of audiences’ interaction in the setting of *Re-visiting "Ah Kong" in Memories* (2008 – 2009) (Photo courtesy: Singapore Art Museum)

This is a series of photographic works of my family members when we visited my fine art collection at Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah (MGTF), Universiti Sains Malaysia; entitled *Welcome Home* (2008) (Figure 2) which features life size photographs of my grandparent. The artwork was installed in front of a colonial style arch, which seemed to have framed us in post-colonial living. We made the visit on the third day of Chinese New Year, the day we traditionally set aside to meet my mother’s relatives. This is the second gathering after my grandfather passed away. The gathering help my family remember him and keep family traditions strong. (Figure 11) For the younger generation like me, I believe one should

know one's family history to stay rooted in the midst of a fast-changing globalised world.

(Kuswandini 2009)

Figure 11: The gathering help my family remember him and keep family traditions strong.

It reminds us to go home often, for without our parent's love, we are poor. The audience is invited to sit on the chair, embrace the pillow in which is embedded a screen that shows the video of Ah-Kong last footage, reminding the audience to ponder and reflect on their own family history and memories. The antique chair is a metaphor of the loneliness I

felt when I travelled alone to Singapore looking for better opportunities, as in Chinese saying, 他方的月亮特别圆 (view of the moon is extraordinary round in foreign land), perhaps it is the same view from any land that we are standing on. Physically the chair is modular as well as the other components of the work; depicting the notion of “the circle and the abyss”. The work is flexible and modular for installation based on a specific site because it easily adapt to any space. (Refer to Figure 12)

Figure 12 showed the installation of *Re-visiting "Ah Kong" in Memories* at Galeri Chandan.

坐站走，思探游；

盼望寻，解染幻。

一切始于“念”。

-法偈-

(Above poem is synonymous for the texts as below.)

Penetrating the horizon of the past,

Heading vertically toward the unknown destination;

Dare to take a turning of life...

With hopes and creations.

(March 2009)

ⁱ *Meeting The South – Dialogue-Thru-Drawing (2009)*, in short MTS, an audience-participation project for *Iskandar Malaysia Contemporary Art Show 2009*'s artist- in-resident at *Danga City Mall*, Johor Baharu. After the 1st MTS, the project extended to different held at different shopping complex in Johor Baharu. URL: <http://picasaweb.google.com/tcliewpg/MeetingTheSouth1DialogueThruDrawings#>

ⁱⁱ *Let the North Meet the South (2009)* is a partner exhibition held during IMCAS 2009 at Danga City Mall, Johor Baharu. The installation included 6 artworks, namely 1. *Looking into (ourselves)* (LTC-SCP-2009-001), 2. *Don't Worry It just T-shirt (jump)* (LTC-PNT-2009-001), 3. *Don't Worry It just T-shirt (hit)* (LTC-PNT-2009-002), 4. *Don't Worry It just T-shirt (swing)* (LTC-PNT-2009-003), 5. *Don't Worry It just T-shirt (kill)* (LTC-PNT-2009-004), 6. *Don't Worry It just game* (LTC-INS-2009-001). URL: <http://tcliew.blogspot.com/2009/03/tan-jong-i-tou-bi-kin-in-imcas-09-lets.html> *Don't Worry It just T-shirt* series is in *Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah's* (MGTF) fine art collection. URL: <http://mgtf.usm.my/viewCollection.php?id=702>

ⁱⁱⁱ For instance, issues of bilateral dispute over *Pedra Branca* and the water supply between Malaysia and Singapore influenced international relationships, economy, politics, development, social impact and other cultural issues. *Pedra Branca* (formerly referred to by Malaysia as *Pulau Batu Puteh* and now as *Batu Puteh*) is an outlying island and also the easternmost point of Singapore. The name means "white rock" in Portuguese, and refers to whitish guano (bird droppings) deposited on the rock. The tension in the relationship is described by Lee Hsien Loong, the Prime Minister of Singapore as *bagai aur dengan tebing* (like the bamboo roots and the river bank) in 1998; Malaysian Former Prime Minister Tun Abdullah Hj. Ahmad Badawi once mentioned that many of us have cross-border family members where most of our relatives are still on the other side of the border and vice versa; therefore the brotherhood between Singapore and Malaysia is immortal and complicated. On the other hand, the Johor – Singapore Causeway is seem pumping oxygenated haemoglobin to maintain the development of two nations; it carries 60 thousands vehicles on a typical day to work, school, export and import trades, tourism and other commercial activities. The causeway can be described as the artery and the vein that carries millions of oxygenated and deoxygenated haemoglobin between two main cities, the *Iskandar Malaysia – Southern Development Corridor*ⁱⁱⁱ and Singapore.

^{iv} **1Malaysia** (pronounced *One Malaysia* in English and *Satu Malaysia* in Malay) is an on-going programme designed by Malaysian Prime Minister Najib Tun Razak on September 16, 2010, calling for the cabinet, government agencies, and civil servants to more strongly emphasize ethnic harmony, national unity, and efficient governance. 1Malaysia stresses national unity and ethnic tolerance. The 2010 values of 1Malaysia as articulated by Najib Razak are perseverance, a culture of excellence, acceptance, loyalty, education, humility, integrity, and meritocracy.

The respond:

A year after the concept's introduction, Mahathir Mohammad reportedly said he "still doesn't understand (masih tidak faham)" the concept. Almost two years later, the public similarly, based on an opinion poll in July 2010, were wary of the concept. In particular, the non-Malays surveyed, according to *The Malaysian Insider*, "were almost split on the Najib administration's national unity agenda with 46 per cent of the respondents believing that the 1Malaysia concept is only a political agenda to win the non-Malay votes," and "only 39 per cent of the non-Malays believed that the concept introduced by Najib after he took over the government was a sincere effort to unite all races in Malaysia".

(resource: Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia)

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Chapter 3: *White-wooden-chair* dreamed to be tree (Comparison)

(This chapter shows the experience of making of *White-wooden-chair*; at a deeper level, it shows the comparison between the meanings of interactions/experiences from a different area of study.)

3.1 The story of *White-wooden-chair*

“Originally the fifty years old wooden chair was black in colour but overnight, it turned into white. The newly transformed *White-wooden-chair* wished to present itself with a new and refreshing look. Its purpose was to overcome its lonely and unhappy life where it was surrounded by four white walls. The *White-wooden-chair* wished to return to the Mother Nature consequently it dreamed to be a tree. Later *White-wooden-chair* grew roots from one of its legs. It has a strong desire to feel the soil, so *White-wooden-chair* planted itself in the middle of the student square surrounded by trees. Overnight *White-wooden-chair*'s has taken roots and have penetrated through the red pavement blocks and absorbed water and minerals from under the ground nourishing itself. Unfortunately *White-wooden-chair* was chasing an unreachable dream; but it has manifested its “being-tree” dream through its imagination in dreamscape because of its strong desire.”

(Written in September 2010)

Figure 13: The *White-wooden-chair* wished to return to the Mother Nature therefore it dreamed to be a tree.

“*White-Wooden-Chair (WWC)* dreamed it was a tree”; is a witty story that describes an installation consisting of a white-painted wooden chair with its tree-like shadow cast on the floor in a public space. It invites passers-by to sit on it and observe the beauty of Mother Nature.

Figure 14: *White-wooden-chair* has a strong desire to feel the soil thus it grew roots in one of its leg. Overnight, *White-wooden-chair's* roots have penetrated through the red pavement; and absorbed water and minerals from underground.

The Returning - Silent dialogue (Ting Chuang, *The Returning - Silent Dialogue* 2010-2011) refers to my

returning to the place that I was born in and to the campus where I was trained as an artist. In 2009, I produced series of installation artworks entitled *Meeting the South* (Ting Chuang, *Meeting the South - Dialogue-Through-Drawing* 2009) (Ting Chuang, *Artist-In-Aquarium*

2009) in the Artist-in-Residence programme organised by the *Iskandar Malaysia Contemporary Art Show (IMCAS)*ⁱ 2009. And his *Re-visiting Ah Kong in Memories* (Ting Chuang, Re-visiting "Ah Kong" in Memories 2008 - 2009) was selected as a finalist in *Singapore Art Show 2009*, the work being exhibited at the Singapore Art Museum. Both were reflections of my experience in Southern Peninsular Malaysia and Singapore.

I am always sensitive to any particular environment that I have stayed in. *Meeting the South* was a manifestation of the uncomfortable experience that I encountered in Johor Baharu. My studio was located smack inside a commercial complex and as such I was exposed to the hustle and bustle of commercial activities and the materialistic world so to speak. *Re-visiting Ah Kong in Memories* was a reflection of that experience of loneliness and being alone in an unfamiliar, foreign place.

Figure 15 shown the circular composition indicates capillary wave force which symbolises the notion of "returning".

I worked on the antique chair which was originally black in colour. When I brought it back to Penang from Johor Baharu, I then made a decision to aggressively to turn the chair into white. I believe that the colour white is a rejuvenating salve for my feelings of alienation staying in the heat and fast paced society in the Southern regionⁱⁱ. I prefer to stay in a friendly environment – a place like Penang.

Formalistically the chair is almost 90 – 100% high key value complimented with few 70 – 80% low key marks. Those marks were made by hatching marks and staining strokes, composed circularly on the wooden seat. The values reflect a positive expression. Additionally the circular composition indicates capillary wave force which symbolises the notion of “returning”. (Figure 15) I broke the chair’s leg then re-assembled it with broken and found wood; and re-constructed it so that it looks like roots are growing from one of the chair’s leg. The process of de-construction and re-construction seemed a violent and aggressive act against the chair but it was done in a carefully thought out plan and design.

3.2 Understanding the notion of interaction/experience.

The attempt at art making and the creation of a work of art in the case of *White-wooden-chair* can be traced through the process of studio practice, by examining the setting, working behaviour, mark-making, presented ideas, conceptual mapping, experimented results and related activities that took place in the studio. It is a platform to practice the constructed methodology and the process of generating behaviourist data; and it is similar to a scientific laboratory conducting experiments and contextualising theories. (Fauzan 2007)

One might ask, “What is the artist’s reaction when he/she was producing such beautiful artworks?”

To answer the question, allow me to quote Charles R. Jensen. He defined art as ‘a set of interactions between the artist and his/her artworks’. The powers of decision making catalyses the artist to create personalised, stylistic and expressive touches in his/her art making, leading to further abstraction then. By this definition, artwork is an evidence of how people make decisions and create meanings. (Jensen 1986)

Furthermore, John Dewey mentioned: “Experience occurs continuously, because the interaction of ‘live creatures’- (*The biological sensory exchange between men*)ⁱⁱⁱ and environmental conditions are involved in the very process of living. Under conditions of resistance and conflicts, aspects and elements of the self and the world that are implicated in this interaction qualify experience with emotions and ideas so that conscious intent emerges.” Quoted from *Art as Experience* by John Dewey (Dewey 1934, 2007)

The above statements describe the co-relationship between “experience and interaction” as the process of art making. The notion of “interaction” as addressed by Jensen refers to the inter-relationship between the artwork and the artist himself – the making of a work of art seen here as an interaction or experience. On the other hand, Dewey had brought this notion of “interaction” further by indicating the psychological process that the audience go through when confronting a work of art; which is defined as the notion of interaction/experience.

One might ask, “How others artist perceive the notion of interaction/experience?”

Conceptual artist, Joseph Kosuth highlighted the important of interaction in human beings’ brain through his argument in *Art After Philosophy*, the ideal of aesthetics being separated from art because aesthetics deal with subconscious interpretation (interaction between left and right hemisphere cerebral). Kosuth's discourse emphasised the idea of making and the so-called "function" of the creation. He viewed physical quality or formal properties from a "linguistic" perspective; he believed that in one’s endeavour of art it is

possible to see things "beyond physics" to fulfil the concept of "man spiritual needs". It reminded me of Piyadasa and Suleiman's *Mystical Concept of Time and Event* manifesto. The manifesto referred to the artist's behaviourist practices (experiences) that are treated as a form of meditation for those who believe in Zen practice or a Minimalism approach in western terminology; which Piyadasa and Suleiman referred to as an "event". Their undertaking can be interpreted as an act of enhancement of Kosuth's theory. (Kosuth, *Art After Philosophy* 1969) (Redza Piyadasa, Suleiman Esa 1974)

One might ask, "How the 'interaction/experience' occurs in our living?"

3.2.1 The notion of interaction/experience in scientific terms

To facilitate further discussions on the notion of interaction/experience; I have adapted learning (also refer as psychology), biology, eastern philosophy and medicine theories. A few models that I have adapted theories from are listed here: *Experiential Learning Theory* (ELT) (Kolb 1984, 2011), Kolb's *Learning Style Inventory* (LSI) 1971, (David A. Kolb, Richard E. Boyatzis, Charalampos Mainemelis 1999) (Hasnul Jamal 2009), *Learning Spaces* (ELS) (Paul Eickmann, Alice Kolb, David Kolb 2002) (Alice Y. Kolb, David A. Kolb 2005), Jean Piaget's *Theory of Cognitive Development Model* (Kolb 1984, 2011) (Wikipedia, Piaget's theory of cognitive development 2011), *Emotion and The Brain Cycle of Learning* (Zull 2002) and *Chakra System Model* (Boyd 1995) (Judith 2002). On the micro level, these adapted theories have its own specific purpose and function. Discussions on the macro level show similar properties which have the potential to correlate significant concepts into a complete new set of theory to describe the art making process.

3.2.2 Experiential Learning Theory

“*Experiential Learning Theory* (ELT) has its intellectual origin from experiential works of Dewey’s philosophical pragmatism, Lewin’s social psychology, and Piaget’s cognitive developmental genetic epistemology forming a unique perspective on learning and development” . So quoted David A. Kolb in his paper entitled, *Experiential Learning Theory: Previous Research and New Directions*, in 1999 at the Department of Organizational Behavior, Weatherhead School of Management, Case Western Reserve University. (David A. Kolb, Richard E. Boyatzis, Charalampos Mainemelis 1999)

ELT is multi-linear and diversity model derived from constructivism learning theory (Wikipedia, Constructivism (learning theory) 2011) (Wikipedia, Learning theory (education) 2011). It describes an active learning process where the student go through experiences through behaviourist practices to understand a new set of knowledge (behaviourism > cognitivism) or following a series of instructions to actualise making (cognitivism > behaviourism). It involves both cognitivism (grasping experience) and behaviourism (transforming experience).

ELT emphasises on gaining experiences through set of instructions. It suggests four dimensions of learning preferences, i.e. concrete experience (feeling) (CE), reflective observation (seeing) (RO), abstract conceptualisation (thinking) (AC) and active experimentation (doing) (AE). “Grasping experience” (the operation) mode refers to concrete experience (CE) and abstract conceptualisation (AC) where these dimensions generate feeling (CE) and thought (AC) and lead to the process of generating of *long-term memory* (LTM) which is stored in the *Hippocampus* part of the brain; in Greek it means horse-shaped (hippo) sea monster (kampos). (Wikipedia, Long-term memory 2011) (Zull, A place for Making Memories 2002) According to the *Atkinson-Shiffrin memory model* (Wikipedia, Atkinson–Shiffrin memory model 2011), LTM is generated through repetition/rehearsal of working

memory (short-term memory). Therefore “transforming experience” integrates both CE and AC dimensions via process-based responds such as observation (RO) and doing (AE) to complete the learning cycle.

3.2.3 Experiential Learning Theory correlates to Lewin, Dewey and Piaget’s model of learning.

Piaget’s model of learning addresses the importance of the learning cycle; the dimensions of “experience and concept” (concrete phenomenal view of the world to abstract constructionist view) and “reflection and action” (active egocentric view to a reflective internalised mode of knowing) forming the basic continuous process of individual thought. Piaget’s model portrays the transition and development from infancy to adulthood. Piaget’s model is significant and leads the major direction of the development in scientific knowledge, especially in education of children. This development takes place in a cycle of “interaction between the individual and the environment” which is similar to the learning model as popularised by Dewey which emphasised the transformation of impulse [experiences] through the learning cycle^{iv}. Lewin’s model emphasises on the “here-and-now” experiences and “feedback” processes^v to conduct the learning based on the interactions from one’s surroundings. (The resources are derived from *Experiential Learning - Experiences as the Sources of Learning and Development* by David Kolb) (Kolb 1984, 2011)

3.2.4 Piaget’s learning model

In his learning model Piaget, arguing through of cognitive development; that learning involves two complementary processes; which are accommodation and assimilation. When

accommodation process dominates assimilation, we imitate and mould the trend from the surrounding. On the other hand, when assimilation predominates over accommodation; we end up with the imposition of well-adapted models or concepts and “interlaying within” environmental realities. In short, Piaget model claims that learning processes involve both frontal cortex and rear cortex.

3.2.5 Learning Style Inventory

Kolb has further developed ELT, through the effort of contextualised research outcomes. Kolb has produced a set of learning properties which is coined as *Learning Style Inventory* (LSI). LSI is a self evaluation test which is able to assess the response of the human brain in learning. LSI test generates varied pattern of scores which represents different types of learning behaviour. Students are asked to rank their preferences for feeling, thinking, acting and reflecting by using *Thurstone Scaling* method^{vi}, 1928. Kolb summarised those preferences and has identified four prevalent learning styles^{vii} -- Diverging, Assimilating, Converging, and Accommodating.

3.2.6 Learning Spaces (Alice Kolb 2005)

Paul Eickmann, the instructional design consultant presented his co-written paper with Alice Kolb and David Kolb, entitled *Designing Learning*, at the *Conference “Managing as Designing: Creating a New Vocabulary for Management Education and Research* in Weatherhead School of Management, Case Western Reserve University, Cleveland, Ohio, in 2002.

The paper investigated the comparison of learning patterns between management and art students from respective colleges and universities. It was an effort to experiment with *Experiential Learning Theory* in art instructional design. Eickmann has theorised that experiential learning is mostly art based on the process of demonstration—practice—production—critique; as a result students have perceived demonstration through Reflective Observation; exercised practices through Abstract Conceptualisation; made production through Active Experimentation; and encountered critiques through Concrete Experience; in short going through the whole process and "touching all bases".

ARTS EDUCATION	MANAGEMENT EDUCATION
aesthetic	scientific
demonstration—practice—production—critique	text driven
recursive	discursive
theory and practice	theory
showing	telling
expression	impression
individualised	batched
diverse faculty	abstract faculty

Table 1 Comparison of Arts Education and Management Education by Paul Eickmann

Eickmann has diagrammatised LSI scores in nine separated regions (nine squares); that he referred to as “Experiential Learning Spaces” (ELS). Each of the region indicates different combinations of specialisations and integrative learning activities where the learner "touches all the bases"--feeling, reflecting, thinking, and acting--in a recursive (circular) process. The designed ELS sufficiently show the diagrammatic data in different category (Table 2).

North-West (NW) acting – feeling (accommodating)	North (N) (back cortex) feeling acting – reflecting (Northerner)	North-East (NE) feeling – reflecting (diverging)
acting West (W) (Westerner) feeling – thinking	Feeling acting Central (C) reflecting (Balancing) thinking	reflecting East (E) (Easterner) feeling – thinking
(converging) acting - thinking South-West (SW)	(Southerner) acting – reflecting thinking South (S) (front cortex)	(assimilating) thinking – reflecting South-East (SE)

Table 2 Designed Learning Spaces (Alice Y. Kolb, David A. Kolb 2005)

3.2.7 “Catalyst theory” instead of “pregnancy theory” in art teaching.

James Elkins also written in his book entitled *Why Art Cannot Be Taught*. Learning is synonymous to a “pregnant woman” who has no theories as to how a fetus is formed in her womb without the doctor’s assistance for nine months. In similar fashion, one can liken this process to how an art teacher can go about providing the right atmosphere for art learning, but he/she is unable control what is going to happen in the created atmosphere. Elkins has coined the term “catalyst theory” to describe the art instructional (constructivism learning theory) instead of the “pregnancy theory” because “students is neither entirely passive nor entirely unaware of the outside world” as Elkins wrote. (Elkins 2001) Elkins in his argument pinpoint the fact that learning art through experiences will lead the student build up their own

characteristic in their making; thus Elkins’ book is entitled: *Why Art Cannot Be Taught*, perhaps it hints at how we should go about in our art teaching. Again Elkins stressed on “interaction/experience”.

3.2.8 Emotion and the Brain Cycle of Learning

James Zull, in his book entitled *The Art of Changing the Brain* discussed about the rationale for “natural learning” which is correlated with the physical functions of brain (cerebral cortex) and the argument of learning cycle; also refers as “The Brain Cycle”. Zull has summarised the matches of two concepts in the table as below:

Important functions of each part of cortex	Match with each stage of the learning cycle	The operational mode
The sensory cortex receives first input from the outside world in form of vision, hearing, touch, position, smells and taste.	This matches with the common definition of Concrete experience, with its reliance on direct physical information from the world.	Grasping experiences
The back integrative cortex is engaged in memory formation and reassembly, language comprehension, developing spatial relationship, and identifying objects, faces, and motion. In short, it integrates sensory information to create images and meaning.	Reflective observation - These functions match well with what happens during reflection, for example, remembering relevant information, day dreaming and free association, developing insights and associations, mentally rerunning experiences, and analysing experiences.	Transforming experiences

<p>The frontal integrative cortex is responsible for short-term memory, problem solving, making decisions, assembling plans for action, assembly of language, making judgments and evaluations, directing the action of the rest of the brain (including memory recall), and organising actions and activities of the entire body.</p>	<p>Abstract conceptualisation - This matches well with the generation of abstractions, which requires manipulation of images and language to create new (mental) arrangements, developing plans for future action, comparing and choosing options, directing recall of past experiences, creating symbolic representations, and replacing and manipulating items held in short-term memory.</p>	<p>Grasping experiences</p>
<p>The motor cortex directly triggers all coordinated and voluntary muscle contractions by the body, producing movement. It carries out the plans and ideas originating from the front integrating cortex, including the actual production of language through speech and writing.</p>	<p>Active experimentation - This matches with the necessity for action in completion of the learning cycle. Active testing of abstractions requires conversion of ideas into physical action, or movements of parts of the body. This includes intellectual activities such as writing, deriving relationships, doing experiments, and talking in debate or conversation.</p>	<p>Transforming experiences</p>

Table 3 shown how a particular stage of the learning cycle seems to fit the capabilities of its matched region of cortex. (adapted from *Rational for Natural Learning in The Art of Changing The Brain* by James Zull)

Zull has further explained the connections between the major areas of cerebral cortex and the role in learning cycle (as we have discussed above) showing the centrality of emotion. Therefore “emotion” functions as bridge for the interconnection between cerebral cortex and limbic cortex. (Figure 16)

One might ask, what is the limbic cortex?

In a nutshell, cerebral cortex functions as powerful cognitive tool for survival called the “neocortex” (new cortex). Neocortex has become a major part of the brain which has evolved at least 5 million to 10 million years ago from the old survival tool – the limbic cortex.

Figure 16 shown the comparison of limbic cortex - inner C-shaped ring of cortex lying beneath an outer ring of neocortex. (adapted from James Zull)

Neocortex structures are like a semi-closed container and cover the limbic cortex. It controls our fear system (amygdala) and pleasure system (basal structures); which trigger simple behaviours like “I want this” and “I don’t want that” systems. (J. E. Zull 2002) It catalyses gut and intuition; and responds to the sublime. The limbic cortex or sublime or

emotion centre plays a significant role of creating the “intention” via the influential experience (emotion) consequently triggering the brain cycle of “natural” learning; as is explained in the meaning of terms “interaction/experience” in biology.

“No matter how much the teacher (who failed to engage with students) appreciates the learning cycle or neuronal networks, a teacher has little hope if his learners don’t ‘feel’ (show the important of experience) engaged.” quoted from *Emotion and the Brain Cycle of Learning* by James Zull. (J. E. Zull, *The Art of Changing the Brain - Enriching Teaching by Exploring the Biology of Learning* 2002)

Figure 17 shown the centrality of emotion between the connection of the neocortex sub-division

3.2.9 Split-brain Theory

Split-brain theory (Sperry 1975) by Roger Sperry had introduced the integration of hemispheric specialisation of human brain functions. The right hemisphere of the brain cortex

excels at nonverbal and spatial tasks; it responds to one's intuitive ability. The left hemisphere of the cortex is dominant in verbal tasks like writing and speaking; it also catalyses the analytic and logical power of the brain. A list of painterly marks are categorised into two groups based on the hemispheric specialisation. For instance, staining marks has a quality of spontaneity therefore it suggests that the artist responded using the right hemisphere of the brain cortex. Hatching marks require organised and analytical attitude hence it suggests responses by the left hemisphere of the brain.

3.2.10 The Chakra Theory

The Chakra originated from the Hindu text which itself is derived from the Sanskrit word for wheel or turning according to traditional Indian medicine; or in Chinese saying, 脉轮 . The concept of Chakra refers to its wheel-like vortices spreading throughout from its centre; from the energy spots our physical body, the layers of the subtle bodies in an ever-increasing fan-shaped formation. The rotating vortices referred to as the spot for reception and transmission of energies. This phenomenal is referred to as aura, halo or paranormal in spiritual practices. There are seven energy spots or Chakra located in the glands along the centre line of the spine whereby each of the energy spots respond to its specific function to the physical body. I have adapted the basic concept of Chakra (as a piece of ancient scientific theory – traditional medicine) for the purpose of correlation between arts and scientific theories. This is because I am unable to see aura colour through peripheral vision^{viii} (side vision) (leading to future development). According to most references aura colour appears in complementary harmony of Chakra colour. Below is a table is showing the summary adaptation of varied references about Chakra system. (Boyd 1995) (Judith 2002) (Regis 1993, 2006) (How To See And Read The Aura n.d.) (VisionRx 2005) (Wikipedia, Chakra 2011)

Chakras (Colour)	Auric sight	Approximate location	Associated activities	Manifested energies	Summarised keywords
Chakra 1: <i>Muladhara</i>	Turquoise	Perineum	Orientation to reality, survival of organism	Earth, Physical identity, oriented to self-preservation	Intention
Chakra 2: <i>Svadhithana</i>	blue	three fingers below CNS	Sexuality, family life, gender relations	Water, Emotional identity, oriented to self-gratification	Imitation
Chakra 3: <i>Manipura</i>	violet	behind solar plexus in CNS	Caring, community, cooperation	Fire, Ego identity, oriented to self-definition	Comparison
Chakra 4: <i>Anahata</i>	pink	behind the heart in CNS	Caring, community, cooperation	Air, Social identity, oriented to self-acceptance	Comprehension
Chakra 5: <i>Vishuddha</i>	orange	behind the pharyngeal hollow in CNS	Creativity, communication	Sound, Creative identity, oriented to self-expression	Implementation
Chakra 6: <i>Ajna</i>	Bright lemon-yellow	in the centre of the brain behind the brows	Intuition, inner guidance	Light, Archetypal identity, oriented to self-reflection	reinvention
Chakra 7: <i>Sahasrara</i>	clear gold metallic	entire cerebral cortex	Wisdom, understanding of life's meaning	Thought, Universal identity, oriented to self-knowledge	creation

Note: CNS – centre nerves system

Table 4 shown the correlation of varied references about Chakra system. (Boyd 1995) (Judith 2002) (Regis 1993, 2006) (VisionRx 2005) (Source 2010)

The meaning of interaction/experience or interaction of ‘live creature’ (*The biological sensory exchange between men*) is broadened and flourished through the adaptation from others areas, namely learning/psychology/biology/eastern medicine theories. The selected theories share in common the structural and conceptual formation whereby:

3.2.10.1 The selected theories are formed in cyclical order, based on those structural formation depicting the notion of cycle of “life”; “life” is refer as “lifespan” that metaphors a complete process, periodic loop and simply just a complete cycle.

3.2.10.2 The selected theories show the complementary phenomenal, equality state, trans-relationship condition and multi-linear network; simply based on human being’s experiences as fundamentals.

3.2.10.3 The selected theories merely sets of knowledge/strategy/method/concept function as “tools” or “systems” to make varied meanings of “experiences” and “interaction”; but both are just merely a bunch of letters like “e, x, p, e, r, i, e, n, c, e, s” and “i, n, t, e, r, a, c, t, i, o, n” symbolising a set of information within a certain group in society. As in Jacques Derrida’s *The Truth in Painting*, he wrote: “it’s enough (too much) to say: abyss (bottomless depth) and satire (full) of the abyss (a vast intellectual or complicated thought)”; paradoxically indicating simply experience of the interaction instead of reading (referring to the reader who read the texts here) the knowledge of the notion of “experience” and “interaction”.

3.2.10.4 Meditation helps us to focus one's mind for a period of time, in silence or with the aid of chanting, for religious or spiritual purposes or as a method of relaxation. As Eickmann, Alice and Kolb have proven learning art is recursion process where it touches all the bases of learning abilities. Dewey, Jensen, Kosuth, Piyadasa and Suleiman referred art making as event and process of learning.

Therefore I coined this argument as the “Cycle of Art Making”; further information will discuss at section 4.2 *Dialogue in the Cycle of Art Making*. (Above selected theories are summarised in Table 5.)

Experiential Learning Theory (Kolb 1984)	The Brain Cycle (Zull 2002)	Dewey's model of experiential learning (Dewey 1934)	The Lewinian Experiential Learning Model (Lewin 1947)	Learning Style Inventory (Kolb 1981)	Learning Space (Alice & David Kolb 2005)	Piaget's model of cognitive and development (Piaget 1955)	Chakra model (Ancient Hindu Medicine)	Summarised keywords
Concrete experience (CE)	Sensory & postsensory	Impulse	Concrete experience	Accommodator	Northerner	Concrete Phenomenalism	Chakra7: <i>Sahasrara</i> (belief)	Creation
				Diverger			Chakra1: <i>Muladhara</i> (root)	Intention
Reflective observation (RO)	Temporal integrative cortex	Observation	Observation and reflection		Diverging	Ikonic learning	Chakra2: <i>Svadhithana</i> (desire)	Imitation
				Easterner	Internalised reflection			
Abstract conceptualisation (AC)	Frontal integrative cortex	Knowledge	Formation of abstract concept & generalisation	Assimilator	Assimilating	Inductive learning	Chakra3: <i>Manipura</i> (ego)	Comparison
				Southerner	Abstract constructionism			
Active experimentation (AE)	Premotor & motor	Judgement/purpose	Testing implication of concepts in new situation	Converger	Converging	Hypotheticadeductive learning	Chakra5: <i>Vishuddha</i> (communication)	Implementation
				Westerner	Active geocentricism			
Concrete experience (CE)	Sensory & postsensory	Impulse	Concrete experience	Accommodator	Accommodating	Enactive learning	Chakra6: <i>Ajna</i> (vision)	reinvention

Table 5: Summary of selected theories can read in hierarchical and cyclical order.

ⁱ *Iskandar Malaysia Contemporary Art Show (IMCAS)* is one of the partners. The project is supported by *Aliya & Farouk Khan collection* and managed by *12 Gallery (Art Space)*. *IMCAS* work together with *Danga City Mall*, one of *Iskandar Malaysia* properties which is expanding their business. *Iskandar Malaysia (IM)*, formerly known as *Iskandar Development Region (IDR)* and *South Johor Economic Region (SJER)* is the main southern development corridor in Johor, Malaysia. The *Iskandar Malaysia* was established on 30 July 2006. The project is administered by *Iskandar Regional Development Authority (IRDA)* and was name after the late Sultan of Johor, *Almarhum Sultan Iskandar*.

ⁱⁱ For instance, issues of bilateral dispute over *Pedra Branca* and the water supply between Malaysia and Singapore influenced international relationships, economy, politics, development, social impact and other cultural issues. *Pedra Branca* (formerly referred to by Malaysia as *Pulau Batu Puteh* and now as *Batu Puteh*) is an outlying island and also the easternmost point of Singapore. The name means "white rock" in Portuguese, and refers to whitish guano (bird droppings) deposited on the rock. The tension in the relationship is described by Lee Hsien Loong, the Prime Minister of Singapore as *bagai aur dengan tebing* (like the bamboo roots and the river bank) in 1998; Malaysian Former Prime Minister Tun Abdullah Hj. Ahmad Badawi once mentioned that many of us have cross-border family members where most of our relatives are still on the other side of the border and vice versa; therefore the brotherhood between Singapore and Malaysia is immortal and complicated. On the other hand, the Johor – Singapore Causeway is seem pumping oxygenated haemoglobin to maintain the development of two nations; it carries 60 thousands vehicles on a typical day to work, school, export and import trades, tourism and other commercial activities. The causeway can be described as the artery and the vein that carries millions of oxygenated and deoxygenated haemoglobin between two main cities, the *Iskandar Malaysia – Southern Development Corridor* and Singapore.

ⁱⁱⁱ John Dewey, who was philosopher, psychologist and education reformer mentioned in his article entitled, *Art as Experience*, in 1934; renewed in 1973 by The John Dewey Foundation. Art is the living and concrete proof the man is capable of restoring consciously, and thus on the plane of meaning, **the union of sense, need, impulse and action characteristic** of the "live creature".

^{iv} *Dewey's Model of Learning* - The formation of purposes is, then, a rather complex intellectual operation. It involves: (1) **observation** of surrounding conditions; (2) **knowledge** of what has happened in similar situations in the past, a knowledge obtained partly by recollection and partly from the information, advice, and warning of those who have had a wider experience; and (3) **judgment**, which puts together what is observed and what is recalled to see what they signify. A **purpose** differs from an original impulse and desire through its translation into a plan and method of action based upon foresight of the consequences of action under given observed conditions in a certain way. (Kolb 1984, 2011)

^v **The Lewinian Model of Action Research and Laboratory Process** – (1) it emphasis on **here-and-now concrete experience** to validate and test abstract concepts. Immediate personal experience is the focal point for learning, giving life, texture and subjective personal meaning to abstract concepts and at the same time providing a concrete, publicly shared reference point for testing the implications and validity of ideas created during the learning process. When human beings share an experience, they can share it fully, concretely, and abstractly. (2) action research and laboratory training are based on **feedback process**. Lewin borrowed the concept of feedback from electrical engineering to describe a social learning and problem-solving process that generates valid information to access deviations from desired goals. This information feedback provides the basic for a continuous process of goal-directed action and evaluation of the consequences of that action. (Kolb 1984, 2011)

^{vi} In psychology, the **Thurstone scale** was the first formal technique for measuring an attitude. It was developed by Louis Leon Thurstone in 1928, as a means of measuring attitudes towards religion. It is made up of statements about a particular issue, and each statement has a numerical value indicating how favorable or unfavorable it is judged to be. People check each of the statements to which they agree, and a mean score is computed, indicating their attitude.

^{vii} **Diverging**. The Diverging style's dominant learning abilities are Concrete Experience (CE) and Reflective Observation (RO). People with this learning style are best at viewing concrete situations from many different points of view. It is labelled "Diverging" because a person with it performs better in situations that

call for generation of ideas, such as a “brainstorming” session. People with a Diverging learning style have broad cultural interests and like to gather information. Research shows that they are interested in people, tend to be imaginative and emotional, have broad cultural interests, and tend to specialize in the arts. In formal learning situations, people with the Diverging style prefer to work in groups, listening with an open mind and receiving personalized feedback.

Assimilating. The Assimilating style’s dominant learning abilities are Abstract Conceptualization (AC) and Reflective Observation (RO). People with this learning style are best at understanding a wide range of information and putting into concise, logical form. Individuals with an Assimilating style are less focused on people and more interested in ideas and abstract concepts. Generally, people with this style find it more important that a theory have logical soundness than practical value. The Assimilating learning style is important for effectiveness in information and science careers. In formal learning situations, people with this style prefer readings, lectures, exploring analytical models, and having time to think things through.

Converging. The Converging style’s dominant learning abilities are Abstract Conceptualization (AC) and Active Experimentation (AE). People with this learning style are best at finding practical uses for ideas and theories. They have the ability to solve problems and make decisions based on finding solutions to questions or problems. Individuals with a Converging learning style prefer to deal with technical tasks and problems rather than with social issues and interpersonal issues. These learning skills are important for effectiveness in specialist and technology careers. In formal learning situations, people with this style prefer to experiment with new ideas, simulations, laboratory assignments, and practical applications.

Accommodating. The Accommodating style’s dominant learning abilities are Concrete Experience (CE) and Active Experimentation (AE). People with this learning style have the ability to learn from primarily “hand-on” experience. They enjoy carrying out plans and involving themselves in new and challenging experiences. Their tendency may be to act on “gut” feelings rather than on logical analysis. In solving problems, individuals with an Accommodating learning style rely more heavily on people for information than on their own technical analysis. This learning style is important for effectiveness in action-oriented careers such as marketing or sales. In formal learning situations, people with the Accommodating learning style prefer to work with others to get assignments done, to set goals, to do field work, and to test out different approaches to completing a project. (David A. Kolb, Richard E. Boyatzis, Charalampos Mainemelis 1999)

^{viii} **Peripheral vision**, or side vision, is that part of vision that detects objects outside the direct line of vision. For instance, when you read a word on a page, you are using your central vision, but it’s your side vision that tells you if the word is at the beginning or end of a sentence, or at the top or bottom of a page. Your peripheral vision also tells you where to look if someone enters the room or if a car is approaching from the side. Like most people, you are probably not aware of the limitations that would exist without peripheral vision, because you are constantly moving your eyes in order to focus with your central vision. The difference between central and peripheral vision becomes apparent when you understand the visual function of the eye. (VisionRx 2005)

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Chapter 4: *White-wooden-chair* invited for nature-feast (comprehension)

(This chapter summarises the result of defining interactions/experiences to become a piece of theoretical framework to discuss the endeavour in this Master of Arts [Visual Art & Design] project. It is partly adopted from unpublished writing assignment entitled, *Simply a Flash of Mind – Gift from the Universe*, written in December 2010)

4.1 Silent dialogue in the nature

White-wooden-chair made many friends from nature. They are the *Busy-Ants*, *Trendy-Mosquitoes*, *Cheerful-Birds*, *Dry-Leaves*, *Rain-Drops*, *Dry-Branches*, *Reflected-Shadows*, *Growing-Trees* and *Blowing-Wind*. Even though *White-wooden-chair* was unable to transform itself to be a real tree but the friendship made it feel like living as a tree again. The friends like to discuss about the surroundings of the campus of Universiti Sains Malaysia

Figure 18: It invites passers-by to sit on it and observe the beauty of Mother Nature.

(USM). Among the topics they discussed were the reactions of USM folks on the sustainable development issue, the motorists' behaviour in USM campus, student daily activities at *Permatang Pelajar* (the installation site) and the enforcement of the *The White Coffin* (USM 2007) campaign. Unfortunately, they were unable to disseminate their views because of the lack of participation from the members of USM campus and their voices continued to be unheard and muted.

White-Wooden Chair invites passers-by to sit on it and observe the beauty of Mother

Nature. Indirectly, *White-Wooden-Chair* is sharing its dreams to remind the public about the concept of sustainability development by re-using and recycling a concept championed by USM itself. It played the role of nature's ambassador. (Dzul kifli 2008)

4.2 The manifesto of "Sustainable Development"

"It's a concept (sustainability development) that does not bind itself to the environment and ecology alone, although that is something that you see", quoted from *Manager@Work: Growing the University of the Future*, Professor Tan Sri Dato' Dzul kifli Abd Razak in an interview with Dorothy Teoh and Aznita Ahmad Pharmy. If the concept of sustainability development does not refer to the environment and ecology; what then is the intention to launch the manifesto?

Professor Dzul kifli, the Vice Chancellor of USM explained the rationale of "Sustainable Development" manifesto to the press:

4.2.1 Transforming instead of "de-constructing or re-constructing" the existing situation and phenomenal; as quoted in Derrida: "This (its models, its concepts, its problems have not fallen from the skies – past endeavour) set forms a system, a greater logic and an encyclopaedia (within certain situation and phenomenal – the specific and unique approach) within which the fine arts would stand out as a particular region (environ - culture). The *Agregation de philosophie* (equivalent of the Ph.D. degree) also forms a history and a system" (Derrida 2007) In other words, we learned from tradition before making any changes, de-constructing is not merely dismantling but to learn the subject from inside-out and vice versa, de-centralised from western master narratives; seeing beyond the subject from the other way round. The concept at its roots encourages the effort of sustaining the value of *globlocal - think globally, act locally*.

- 4.2.2 Blue Ocean Strategy is derived from a structuralist approach; which is the high growth and profits an organization can generate by creating new demand in an uncontested market space (W. Chan Kim, Renee Mauborge, 刘华才 (translated) 2007). It has been adapted to practice sustainability development in USM campuses. In the interview Professor Dzul kifli mentioned, “not competing head-on (existing competitions) but competing in the area you think you are not relevant (potential uncontested area)” Professor Dzul kifli is leading USM into the transforming state, by adapting *Eliminate-Reduce-Raise-Create Grid (four actions framework)* to interpret the situation; USM is **eliminating** cultural hierarchy within the campus; **reducing** outsourcing practices to complete tasks; **raising** “in-source” practices by cooperating with internal experts; and **creating** volunteering culture among the members of its campus. The concept encourages the effort of sustaining the niches and strengths, positioning the University towards trans-disciplinary practice.
- 4.2.3 Since USM is practicing applied research within limited technology platform where “our science has always been focused on applied, (applying somebody else's basic” as Professor Dzul kifli mentioned); the push now is to get back to basics, return to the fundamentals to assure a boarder platform for the next departure. It is a metaphor for the “experiences” to look back to our roots, culture and heritage. The concept encourages the effort of sustaining our identities and cultural values towards a truly *Malaysia* vision.
- 4.2.4 Developing human capital is a big part of the effort to promote the virtue of a human being. Hasnul wrote: “We are the containers (human capital) and the contained (virtue), intertwined in a reservoir of love (metaphor for complementing), far larger and finer than what we can imagine with the aid of our naked perception.” (Hasnul Jamal 2006) Virtue, phrased in a different way is referred to as; *Rahman* and *Rahim* in

the Muslim tradition; 仁 (humanity) in Confucius; 德 (moral) in Daoism; *Sanatana Dharma* (moral duty or Hinduism) and in theological terms, virtue in Christianity are faith, hope and love. (Wikipedia 2011) The concept underlines the effort of sustaining the quality of life, which is being practiced since our ancestors' time.

4.3 “Sustainable Development” in *White-wooden-chair*

Figure 19: Study of the installation site (reflected shadow and painted shadow)

White-wooden-chair has created an awareness of re-using and recycling in sustainability terms. It has created this awareness among the inhabitants of the campus through interaction during the whole period it was installed for approximately three months in the middle of *Permatang Pelajar*, the student square of Universiti Sains Malaysia. More precisely, the installation site is the converging point of three authorities, namely the School

of The Arts, the Dewan Budaya (The Cultural Hall) and Jabatan Keselamatan (The Security Unit) of USM. It can be said that the *White-wooden-chair* project was working in controversial and complicated phenomenal and it was only through the adaptation of influential factors that it expanded and grew an alternative methodology to achieve success in the project.

Figure 20: Satellite view of White-wooden-chair installation site.

As Professor Dzulkifli mentioned, “That tagline - 'University in the Garden' is now no longer just an aesthetic tagline, it's not just about how beautiful it is, and it has got other subliminal concepts attached to it. Higher education must be about the diversity of ideas, supremacy of ideas; it must be about people of different cultures and different beliefs, different principles, interacting with one another.”

The pun-loaded statement or the witty tagline - “*White-wooden-chair* has dreamed it was a tree” simply addresses the concept of recycling and reuse in sustainability terms. As such, the tagline touches on the boarder scope of the audience. In a deeper way, “*White-wooden-chair* has dreamed it was a tree” addresses, hints, reminds and make jokes to its subliminal concepts where it triggers the anticipation and performativity (Wikipedia, Performativity 2011) or in other way words, the interaction and experience of both the audience and me.

At a micro level based on form “*White-wooden-chair*” points to many things; “White” refers to the “white wall practices” or the “white cube” that symbolises the norm in gallery curatorial practices. “Wooden” as in material reminds us about the Pre-Industrialised Age before 17th century where firewood and timber were the major consumption products for “metropolitanisation”. A “chair” is a symbol of power and knowledge as derived from Joseph Kosuth’s *One and Three Chair* (1965) (Kosuth, One And Three Chairs 1965) and acts as an important icon of conceptual art. For all intents and purposes *White-wooden-chair* is a piece of art even though its physical appearance does not “look” like “artwork”. The phrase “*White-wooden-chair*” can be read as; a manipulated chair-like object proposed as a piece of artwork based on its historical value which is declared as a gallery-based sculptural piece.

“I don’t have to tell you that for the general public and for you, the refined public, a Dadaist is equivalent of a ‘leper’. But that is only a manner of speaking...” – Tristan Tzara, 1922. (Motherwell 2010)

At a macro level, the statement; “*White-wooden-chair* has dreamed it was a tree” is synonymous to the gallery-based artworks installed in the middle of the crowd; a paradoxical statement inquiring the importance and value of a piece of contemporary artwork within the

local art scene. In short, *White-wooden-chair* project is partly searching for the meaning of its making.

One might ask, “How the *White-wooden-chair* touches the notion of sustainable development?” This question can be thus answered as below:

4.3.1 Transforming from creator-centred and audience-centred to a hybrid form of creator/audience-centred. The manipulation of *White-wooden-chair* embeds multiple layers of my expressions, thought patterns and its origin (the chair) discussed in the previous chapters. While *White-wooden-chair* invites the public to sit on it and to appreciate the beauty of nature, it still remained itself, a chair offering the basic functions of a chair. The contrasts of both features create a unique experience and myriad

Figure 21 indicates the signals and signifiers such as; wooden chair and tree, artist and audiences, interior and exterior, artwork and science university, manmade and natural, western (approach) and eastern (philosophy), facilitating and participating, et cetera; which unveiled the meanings behind the “vessels” in physical reality.

possibilities of interactions between the audience and *White-wooden-chair*.

4.3.2 Whereas most of the seminal artworks like Kosuth’s chair, Piyadasa’s chair and Ai Weiwei’s chairs depict power, authority and ownership I choose to focus on the

unique meaning of the chair. Instead of expressing the impact of “colonisation”, I choose to share my feelings of thankfulness and appreciation of the tradition of beauty in the arts and culture. (Further discussions in the next section.)

4.3.3 Going back to basics, the making of *White-wooden-chair* is derived and inspired by Ah-Kong’s teachings, the moral of the lessons learned that underscores the belief that every existence has its meaning and reason to be. In section 1.1 *Ah-Kong’s Teaching*, I have addressed the rationale *White-wooden-chair*; which was the process of pondering upon the meaning of interactions and experience. In this context, *White-wooden-chair* is the agent that triggered the research output through the art making, curatorial processes, experimentations, data collection and contextualisation.

4.3.4 Sustaining the quality of life, *White-wooden-chair* embraces Lao Zi’s teachings in the context of the laws of complementary (对立转化); simply wooden chair and tree, artist and audience, interior and exterior, artwork and science university, manmade and natural, western (approach) and eastern (philosophy), facilitating and participating, et cetera; as the signal and signifier to unveil the teachings behind the “vessels” in physical reality.

作亭者谁？山之僧智仙也。名之者谁？太守自谓也。宋·欧阳修《醉翁亭记》

(The Old Drunkard's Arbour was built by a Buddhist priest, called “Deathless Wisdom” , who lived among these hills; and who received the above name from the Governor, Ow-yang Hein himself.) (Ow-yang Hein, in *The Old Drunkard’s Arbour*, 1045 Soong Dynasty) (Giles 2007)

4.4 Dialogue in the *Cycle of Art Making*

The Old Drunkard, *Ow-yang Hein* named the harbour as “Old Drunkard’s Arbour” because of the beauty of the *Shantong* hillside; the appreciation of the hillside scenery can make one drown in its “beauty”. As mentioned in his writings, men travelled far from the Luling town to savour the attractive hillside scenery. It is a metaphor of the importance of travelling from town to the destination; as lesson or meditation for practising the concept of *Doctrine of Meaning*. (陈鼓应 2003) (百度百科 Baidu 2010) (Wikipedia, *Doctrine of the Mean* 2010) (Wikipedia, 维基百科, 自由的百科全书 2010)

The wisdom of hiking with his men is similar to the modern concept of team-building spirit; working together to achieve certain objectives, sharing of hard work, joyfulness and enjoyment of making. Conceptually, interpreting *The Old Drunkard's Arbour*; is like the "wine" of the beautiful *Shantong* hillside. For me, it is a piece of installation art of Mother Nature. *Ow-yang Hein* and his men ventured into Mother Nature. But the audience and the visitors; how well were they inspired by the installation piece or granted wisdom by the Mother Nature?

Joseph Kosuth's discourse in *Art After Philosophy* (Kosuth, *Art After Philosophy* 1969) emphasised the idea of making and the so-called "function" of the creation. Kosuth viewed physical quality or formal properties from a "linguistic" perspective; he believed that in one's endeavour in art it is possible to see things "beyond physics" to fulfil the concept of "man's spiritual needs". Looking on the “function” of the creation of *The Old Drunkard's Arbour* and *Art After Philosophy*; both explained the rationale how artwork offers series of thought to its audiences.

By this definition, reading a piece of artwork is similar to the metaphoric meaning of “peeling an onion” which has many layers; where we start our study from the outer layer and

then move inwards to the inner contents of the onion. At the end of the “peeling”, there are just a pile of onion skins. I have proposed a list of the art making process coined as “Cycle of Art-making” which is adapted from Experiential Learning Theories (Kolb 1984, 2011) and Chakra theories. (see *Table 1: Summary of selected theories.*) The sequence of art making are addressed by such learning concepts as; intention (root), imitation (desire), comparison (ego), comprehension (love), implementation (communication), reinvention (vision) and creation (belief). Below are the contents of the “Cycle of Art-Making”.

4.4.1 Intention (root)

According to Oxford Dictionary, intention is defined as a thing intended; an aim or plan. By this definition, the artist has a new thought and idea to produce a piece of work. It also refers to the artist starting with the fundamental actions of his thought and expression. The artist responds immediately to this discovery through sketches, photo-documentation, collecting object or materials, and others preliminary actions that were triggered by his very first thoughts of art making. I have implemented “Cycle of Art Making” in this thesis writing for the sake of experiment. *Chapter 1: Seed of White-wooden-chair* describes the very beginning of the idea of *White-wooden-chair*.

4.4.2 Imitation (desire)

Imitation (Oxford Dictionary) refers to the action of using someone or something as a model; the act of copying. Learning from the Old Masters, Mother Nature, happenings and piece of experience; sequences of instructions or directions. *Chapter 2: Growing of White-wooden-chair* addresses the “imitation” from my past experiences, as I treat it as an awakening signal in my life.

4.4.3 Comparison (ego)

Oxford dictionary defined comparison as a consideration or estimate of the similarities or dissimilarities between two things or people. It also refers as; identifying other research that is similar to one's proposed research. It provides the opportunity to analyse the differences and similarities among the surveyed research. *Chapter 3: White-wooden-chair dreamed to be tree* shows the experience of making of *White-wooden-chair*; at a deeper level, it shows the comparison between the meanings of interactions/experiences from a different area of study.

4.4.4 Comprehension (love)

The common meaning of comprehension refers to the ability to understand something. (Oxford Dictionary). It is the process of gaining knowledge through comparison, so that one is able to experiment with the knowledge in different conditions and situations to verify its relevancy. *Chapter 4: White-wooden-chair invited for nature-feast* - which is this chapter, summarises the result of defining interactions/experiences to become a piece of theoretical framework to discuss the endeavour in this Master of Arts (Visual Art & Design) project.

4.4.5 Implementation (communication)

According to Oxford Dictionary, implementation refers to the process of putting a decision or plan into effect or execution. Implementing self-developed theory in contemporary industry to gain endorsement from peer practitioners; bridging practicality and theoretical. *Chapter 5: White-white-chair extended the experiences* reviews the interaction from the audience, the School of The Arts and my response; bringing the "model" into practice.

4.4.6 Reinvention (vision)

Reinvention changes (something) so much that it appears to be entirely new. (Oxford Dictionary) It is compiling specimens from other endeavours in the same area of

studies. It involves contextualising research outcome as an effort to create new knowledge. *Chapter 6: White-wooden-chair actualised its (my) dream* reported the result of the curatorial of Master of Arts (Visual Art & Design) Thesis Exhibition and Research Outcome Exhibition by the rest of the studio members. The curatorial strategy is derived from the experimented theories and methodology where I have brought it into a deeper level.

4.4.7 Creation (belief)

Oxford Dictionary defined creation as the action or process of bringing something into existence. Creation in Cycle of Art Making refers to the outcome of re-invention which is potentially suggesting alternative and workable approach in respective area; pioneering among the industry. *Chapter 7: White-wooden-chair is revolving from “The returning” to “Meeting the South”* is the afterthought for the endeavour in this Master of Arts (Visual Art & Design) project. Partly it is harvesting the fruit of my effort; completed the Chinese saying, 种瓜得瓜，种豆得豆。明·施耐庵《水浒传》第四十五回 (if a man plants melons he will reap melons; if he sows beans, he will reap beans).

4.5 Dialogue of Kosuth's chair, Piyadasa's chair, Ai Weiwei's chairs, and *White-wooden-chair*.

In this section, I chose Kosuth's chair (Kosuth, One And Three Chairs 1965), Piyadasa's chair (Piyadasa 1977), Ai Weiwei's chairs (Weiwei 2007), and *White-wooden-chair* (Ting Chuang 2010-2011) as specimens for further discussions. I have subscribed *Visual Sampling Method*ⁱ 2.0 and 3.0 (Hasnul Jamal Saidon, Liew Ting Chuang 2008 - ?) to

make an in-depth analysis that potentially generates comparative studies of selected specimens.

This short brief gives basic idea of the selected specimens. The analysis contains two parts:

4.5.1 Formal properties reviews

Visual Sampling Method 2.0 (VSM 2.0) is subscribed to compare the physical quality of selected specimens through designed diagrams to show the difference. The review will be based on genre, year produced, medium, colour, treatment, subject-matter and thematic studies. It is also based on comparative cultural studies method (Karl Deutsch, Pentti Routio(adapted) 2007) (Wikipedia, Comparative research 2011). In VSM 2.0 the barcode-like diagrams showed different “patterns”, those “patterns” are the comparative data; it helps curators or researchers do commentary. It is an invented scientific approach for visual studies, and still in experimental stage under Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah (MGTF).

4.5.2 Conceptual reviews

Visual Sampling Method 3.0 (VSM 3.0) is a conceptual instrument to generate statistical data based on formal properties and basic elements of artworks. VSM 3.0 is used as an investigative instrument to generate additional data such as the proficiency of curatorial, audience interpretation & accessibility of audience. VSM 3.0 makes comparative studies on designed graph with five diagrams, arranged in hierarchical order. The x & y-axis form rectangular diagrams that horizontally show symmetrical relationship and vertically show hierarchy of any desired parameter.

The *Cycle of Art Making* fit in y-axis to review the complexity of a process. Split-brain theory (Sperry 1975) is adapted on the x-axis, based on the integration of

hemispheric specialisation of human brain functions. The right hemisphere of the brain cortex excels at nonverbal and spatial tasks; it responds to one's intuitive ability. The left hemisphere of the cortex is dominant in verbal tasks like writing and speaking; it also catalyses the analytic and logical power of the brain. A list of selected keywords are categorised into two groups based on the hemispheric specialisation. Those keywords derived from different layers of studies such as audience perceiving approaches, mode of making, data collection method, presentation strategy and area of studies. The table below shows the placements of keywords according to Split-brain theory.

	left hemisphere cerebral (analytic/logical power)	right hemisphere cerebral (intuitive ability)
Audience perceiving approaches	Cognitivism	Behaviourism
Mode of making	Audiences-centred	Creator-centred
Data collection method	Research-oriented	Review-oriented
Presentation approach	Conceptual approach	Formalist approach
Area of studies	Science	The Arts

Table 6 shows the placements of keywords according to Split-brain theory (Sperry 1975).

4.6 The review

人知从太守游而乐，而不知太守之乐其乐也。醉能同其乐，醒能述以文者，太守也。太守谓谁？庐陵欧阳修也。(So the Governor's friends; they rejoiced with him, though they do not understand at what is that he rejoiced in. Drunk he can rejoice with them; sober he can discourse with them; such is the Governor. And should you ask who this Governor is, I reply "Ow-yang Hein of Lu-ling.") (Giles 2007)

The selected three chairs by different artists are installed in different situations and conditions:

- a. **Kosuth's chair** – installed according to gallery setting, inviting the audience to observe perhaps touch, a practice usually not allowed in museums.
- b. **Piyadasa's chair** – installed outdoor, required reflected shadow, invites audience observation and to walk around the installation 360 degrees.
- c. **Ai Weiwei's chairs** - installed scattered around the showroom, inviting audience to sit on it and contemplate.
- d. ***White-wooden-chair*** – installed in the middle of student square, required reflected shadow, and invites the audience to sit on the chair.

Kosuth's chair

Piyadasa's chair

Ai Weiwei's chair

White-wooden-chair

Figure 22: Selected artworks as specimens, Josef Kosuth, *One And Three Chair* (1965), Redza Piyadasa, *A Matter of Time* (1977), Ai Weiwei's *Fairytale-1001 Qing Dynasty wooden chairs* (2007), Liew Ting Chuang, *The Returning – Silent Dialogue* (2010-2011).

4.6.1 Formal review (VSM 2.0)

genre	year	medium	colour	treatment	subject-matter	thematic
drawing	1950 - 1954	projection mobile phone web-based computer coding HVS tape video footage graphic motion vector graphic bitmap graphic	primary colour	marks	figures	formalism
sketchbook/ scrapbook	1955 - 1959	ready-made polystyrene PVC glass concrete	secondary colour	texts	portraits	architectural
	1960 - 1964	pastel of paris clay metal stoneware marble wood/timber			built	the economy
painting	1965 - 1969	chromogenic print blue print darkroom colour print galetin silver print offset lithography laser printing inkjet printing xerography stencil silkscreen image-transferring lithography aquatint drypoint etching engraving linoleum wood engraving woodcut	tertiary colour	diagrams	foods	politics
		adhesive aerosol paint wood filler emulsion gross paint bitumen vinyl paint tempera oil paint primer gesso acrylic fabric die gouache transparent watercolour watercolour chinese ink indian ink marker correction liquid pen crayon oil pastel chalk pastel charcoal graphite coloured pencil pencil metal plastic sheet polycarbonate sheet plywood tarpaulin linen cloth canvas tape			flora & fauna/ creatures/cells	the Malaysia art scene
prints	1970 - 1974	others type of paper matt photo paper gross photo paper ammonia paper corrugated board board tracing paper hand-made paper rice paper coated paper coldpressed paper hotpressed paper simili paper	high-key value	graphics	electronic & digital devices	traditional/ cultural
sculpture	1975 - 1979				stationary & books	love & relationship
photography	1980 - 1984		low-key value	illustration	toys/games/ collectable items	campaign/ ideology
	1985 - 1989				jewellery/ fashion/ accessories	social issue
installation	1990 - 1994		pure intensity	pictorials	furniture/interior	identity/self-improvement
	1995 - 1999				decoration/ pattern	sexuality
computer generated imagery	2000 - 2004		dulled intensity	found objects	artifacts	leisure/ entertainment
	2005 - 2009				landscapes	religion/worship
public installation	2010 - 2014				others	the environment
	2015 - 2019					

Visual Sampling Method 2.0, Hazrul J Saidon & TC Uiew, 2008
One And Three Chairs (1965) Joseph Kosuth

Figure 23 shown the VSM 2.0 data of Kosuth's chair.

genre	year	medium	colour	treatment	subject-matter	thematic
drawing	1950 - 1954	projection mobile phone web-based computer coding HVS tape video footage graphic motion vector graphic bitmap graphic	primary colour	marks	figures	formalism
sketchbook/ scrapbook	1955 - 1959	resin made polystyrene PVC glass concrete pastel of paris clay metal stoneware marble wood/timber chromogenic print blue print			portraits	architectural
painting	1960 - 1964		secondary colour	texts	built	the economy
	1965 - 1969				foods	politics
prints	1970 - 1974	darkroom colour print galeatin silver print offset lithography laser printing inkjet printing xerography stencil silkscreen image transferring lithography aquatint drypoint etching engraving linoleum wood engraving woodcut adhesive aerosol paint wood filler emulsion gross paint bitumen vinyl paint tempera oil paint primer gesso	tertiary colour	diagrams	flora & fauna/ creatures/cells	the Malaysia art scene
sculpture	1975 - 1979				electronic & digital devices	traditional/ cultural
	1980 - 1984		high-key value	graphics	stationary & books	love & relationship
photography	1985 - 1989				toys/games/ collectable items	horror/violence
installation	1990 - 1994	fabric die gouache transparent watercolour watercolour chinese ink indian ink marker correction liquid pen crayon oil pastel chalk pastel charcoal graphite coloured pencil pencil metal plastic sheet polycarbonate sheet plywood tarpaulin linen cloth canvas tape	low-key value	illustration	jewellery/ fashion/ accessories	surrealistic
computer generated imagery	1995 - 1999				furniture/interior	campaign/ ideology
public installation	2000 - 2004		pure intensity	pictorials	decoration/ pattern	social issue
video art	2005 - 2009	others type of paper matt photo paper gross photo paper ammonia paper corrugated board board tracing paper hand-made paper rice paper coated paper coldpressed paper hotpressed paper simili paper			artifacts	identity/self- improvement
audience interactive performance	2010 - 2014		dulled intensity	found objects	landscape	sexuality
	2015 - 2019				others	leisure/ entertainment
						religion/worship
						the environment

Visual Sampling Method 2.0. Hazrul J Saidon & TC Liew, 2008
A Matter of Time (1977) Redza Piyadasa

Figure 24 shown the VSM 2.0 data of Piyadasa's chair.

genre	year	medium	colour	treatment	subject-matter	thematic
drawing	1950 - 1954	projection mobile phone web-based computer coding HVS tape video footage graphic motion vector graphic bitmap graphic	primary colour	marks	figures	formalism
sketchbook/ scrapbook	1955 - 1959	handmade			portraits	architectural
	1960 - 1964	polystyrene PVC glass concrete pastel of paris clay metal stoneware marble wood/timber chromogenic print blue print	secondary colour	texts	built	the economy
painting	1965 - 1969	darkroom colour print galein silver print offset lithography laser printing inkjet printing xerography stencil silkscreen			foods	politics
prints	1970 - 1974	image-transferring lithography aquatint drypoint etching engraving linoleum wood engraving woodcut adhesive	tertiary colour	diagrams	flora & fauna/ creatures/cells	the Malaysia art scene
sculpture	1975 - 1979	aerosol paint wood filler emulsion gross paint bitumen vinyl paint tempera oil paint primer gesso acrylic fabric die gouache			electronic & digital devices	traditional/ cultural
photography	1980 - 1984	transparent watercolour watercolour chinese ink indian ink marker correction liquid pen crayon oil pastel chalk pastel charcoal graphite coloured pencil pencil metal plastic sheet polycarbonate sheet plywood tarpaulin linen cloth canvas tape	high-key value	graphics	stationary & books	trend/pop-cultural
	1985 - 1989	others type of paper matt photo paper gross photo paper ammonia paper corrugated board board tracing paper hand-made paper rice paper coated paper coldpressed paper hotpressed paper simili paper			toys/games/ collectable items	love & relationship
installation	1990 - 1994		low-key value	illustration	jewellery/ fashion/ accessories	patriotism
computer generated imagery	1995 - 1999				furniture/interior	horror/violence
public installation	2000 - 2004		pure intensity	pictorials	decoration/ pattern	surrealistic
	2005 - 2009				artifacts	campaign/ ideology
video art	2010 - 2014		dulled intensity	found objects	landscape	social issue
audience interactive performance	2015 - 2019				others	identity/self-improvement

Fairytale-1001 Qing Dynasty wooden chairs (2007), Ai Weiwei

Figure 25 shown the VSM 2.0 data of Ai Weiwei's chair.

genre	year	medium	colour	treatment	subject-matter	thematic
drawing	1950 - 1954	projection mobile phone web-based computer coding HVS tape video footage graphic motion vector graphic bitmap graphic	primary colour	marks	figures	formalism
sketchbook/ scrapbook	1955 - 1959	ready-made polystyrene			portraits	architectural
	1960 - 1964	glass concrete pastel of paris clay metal stoneware marble	secondary colour	texts	built	the economy
painting	1965 - 1969	wood/lambar chromogenic print blue print			foods	politics
prints	1970 - 1974	darkroom colour print galeatin silver print offset lithography laser printing inkjet printing xerography stencil silkscreen image-transferring lithography aquatint drypoint etching	tertiary colour	diagrams	flora & fauna/ creatures/cells	traditional/ cultural
sculpture	1975 - 1979	engraving linoleum wood engraving woodcut adhesive aerosol paint wood filler emulsion gross paint bitumen			electronic & digital devices	trend/pop- cultural
	1980 - 1984	vinyl paint	high-key value	graphics	stationary & books	love & relationship
photography	1985 - 1989	tempera oil paint primer gesso			toys/games/ collectable items	patriotism
	1990 - 1994	fabric die gouache transparent watercolour watercolour chinese ink indian ink marker correction liquid pen crayon oil pastel chalk pastel charcoal graphite coloured pencil	low-key value	illustration	jewellery/ fashion/ accessories	horror/violence
installation	1995 - 1999	metal plastic sheet polycarbonate sheet plywood tarpaulin linen cloth canvas tape			furniture/interior	surrealistic
computer generated imagery	2000 - 2004	others type of paper matt photo paper gross photo paper ammonia paper corrugated board board tracing paper hand-made paper rice paper coated paper coldpressed paper hotpressed paper simili paper	pure intensity	pictorials	decoration/ pattern	campaign/ ideology
public installation	2005 - 2009				artifacts	social issue
video art	2010 - 2014				landscape	identity/self- improvement
	2015 - 2019		dulled intensity	found objects	others	sexuality
audience interactive performance						leisure/ entertainment
						religion/worship
						the environment

The Returning (Silent Dialogue) (2010-2011) Liew Ting Chuang

Figure 26 shown the VSM 2.0 data of White-wooden-chair.

Kosuth's chair	Piyadasa's chair	Ai Weiwei's chair	White-wooden-chair
Genre			
Installation that fit to gallery practice. Installation instruction is the key reference to convey the concept.	Even though installed outside the gallery, but it considered as single unit sculptural item.	Scatted at the showroom for audiences to sit on it and contemplation.	Installed in the public space for the purpose of inviting audiences' participation.
Year produced			
Late 1960's: "The Sixties" denoting the complex of inter-related cultural and political trends across the globe, or referred as Cultural Decade.	Late 1970's: Awareness of socio-cultural, rise of Feminism, awareness of civil right, establishment of cognitive sciences, Apollo 14 landed on moon, the birth of modern computing.	Late 2000's: Globalisation age, abuse of social media, IT age, into cosmology and metaphysic generation, into the transition of western to eastern domain, environmental awareness.	Late 2000's: Globalisation age, abuse of social media, IT age, into cosmology and metaphysic generation, into the transition of western to eastern domain, environmental awareness.
Mediums			
Readymade from commodity for materialism commentary.	Readymade from commodity for anti-form ideology.	Readymade antique collected from the past symbolised power and ownership	Readymade antique collected from the past depicted the sense of belonging.
Colour			
High key value, pure intensity; suggested the object as original.	Tertiary colour scheme, high key value, pure intensity; suggested manipulation has made with objective.	Tertiary colour scheme, low key value, dulled intensity; suggested the appearances of aged antique chair had originally preserved.	High key value, pure intensity; suggested aggressively manipulated based on fetish behaviour and attitude.
Treatment			
Texts, pictorial and found object: suggested constructed narrative is developed and make link in among them.	Texts, graphic and found object; suggested constructed cognitive structure is developed to address audiences with objective.	Found objects; his collecting effort as the reason to demonstrate activism	Marks, graphic and found objects; suggested aggressive behaviourist on the making that capture personal touch.
Subject-matter			
Furniture; commonality product, flappable chair	Furniture; 70's Dining chair	Furniture; Qing Dynasty chairs	flora & fauna, electronic device, furniture: 50's handmade dining chair.
Thematic			
1. Trend/Pop culture: respond to commodity. 2. campaign/ideology: pioneering new perspective in conceptual making; expanded the function of art & view art from 'linguistic' perspective.	1. The Malaysia art scene: respond to picture-making culture in 70's. 2. Trend/Pop culture: adaptation of Western-centric widely spread in 70's. 3. campaign/ideology: manifesto of thinking-artist ideology.	1. Politics: respond to autonomous of China media; scepticism toward authority; Golden Shield Project (internet censorship) banned of website vendors like Yahoo! Hongkong, BBC News, Chinese Wikipedia, Facebook, Google and etc; echo of	1. Love & relationship: express the sense of belonging and returning to hometown and campus. 2. Campaign/ideology: align to sustainability manifesto of USM. 3. Identity/Self improvement: personal reflection through life

		<p>Tiananmen Square protest.</p> <p>2. Traditional/cultural: reminds us, especially the people of Republic China about the Qing Dynasty ruling system phenomenon; made a synonymous of current government situation.</p> <p>3. Campaign/ideology: Pun and paradox tone to remind audiences about the freedom of expression.</p> <p>4. Social issue: Young generation of China are leading toward the argument of freedom in many aspects in social life.</p>	<p>experiences.</p> <p>4. The environment: create awareness of care for nature.</p>
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Table 7 shown the comparison result from VSM 2.0. (Kosuth, *One And Three Chairs* 1965) (Piyadasa 1977) (Weiwei 2007) (Ting Chuang 2010-2011)(Kosuth, *Art After Philosophy* 1969) (Sabapathy 2001) (Colonnello 2007) (Zhang 1996-2011) (Wikipedia, Ai Weiwei 2011) (Sheridan 2011) (Mu 2007)

Ai Weiwei's *Fairytales-1001 Qing Dynasty Wooden Chairs* was part of his Fairytales (童话) series in Documenta 12. Therefore above readings referred to the intertextuality of two other works entitled, *Templates* and *Fairytales-1001 Chinese Visitors*.

“I think people will just pass them, or stop by and look at them, and think about them. Yes, there will be seats there, people can sit around... To me, events such as Documenta or Fairytales are like temples...” Ai Weiwei said. (Colonnello 2007)

4.6.2 Conceptual review (VSM 3.0)

The result of VSM 2.0 reflected surface review of selected specimens. It should pair with the result of VSM 3.0 which will give a better picture of the specimens.

Figure 27: VSM 3.0 data of the comparison of selected specimens.

By carefully following the trail from top to bottom, one will notice the lists of keywords that described the specimens. Below are the lists of keywords traced from the provided map. Those keywords are aids for summarising information of the specimens.

4.6.2.1 Kosuth's chair

a. Areas of studies

Keywords: The Arts – reinvention (vision)

Suggested statements:

Kosuth's chair pioneered the adaptation of structuralism approach to convey his idea of three chairs; any wooden folded chair, a photograph of the particular folded chair and an enlarged photograph of the definition of chair as found in the dictionary.

b. Presentation approach

Keywords: conceptual & formalism approach – creation (belief)

Suggested statements:

Kosuth's chair demonstrated a new approach of art making, referred to as conceptual art. It attracted many followers expanding conceptual art into other branches such as installation art, performance art, public art, net.art, electronic art et cetera. On the other hand, Kosuth's *Art After Philosophy* (1969) essay has brought up new perspective of aesthetics, referred to as anti-aesthetic ideology, an important contribution in art today.

c. Data collection method

Keywords: review-oriented – implementation (social)

Suggested statements:

Kosuth's chair could be referred to as kitsch commentary of commodity culture, pop culture in The Sixties and Post-war celebrations, Abstract Expressionism, Pop art, the development of world economy, rock and roll and the nurturing of cultural media.

d. Mode of making

Keywords: creator-centred – reinvention (vision)

Suggested statements:

Kosuth attempted to share his vision to the society which was drowning in materialism behaviour, ritualised by buying power. This personal statement became a strong characteristic in conceptual art that we refer to today. Kosuth's "conceptual art" style is subscribed to by Malaysia contemporary artists who try to manifest social commentary in their art, referred to as "Issue based art" (IBA)ⁱⁱ here.

e. Audience perceiving method

Keywords: cognitivism – implementation (social)

Suggested statements:

Kosuth's chair has strong narrative content through the representation of found objects, photographs and texts. It encourages audiences to read the trans-connectivity nature of Kosuth's chair. It functions as communication medium as well. (Frank 2009) (Wikipedia, One and Three Chairs 2010) (Wikipedia, Joseph Kosuth 2010)

4.6.2.2 Piyadasa's chair

a. Areas of studies

Keywords: The Arts – reinvention (vision)

Suggested statements:

Piyadaya's chair invites discussions about value, space and time in scientific approach as well as understanding of visual principles. Piyadasa invited his audiences to observe the demonstration through his art making.

b. Presentation approach

Keywords: conceptual approach – reinvention (vision)

Suggested statements:

Piyadasa challenged the Chinese artists (who only make and confine themselves to Chinese paintings) with his paradoxical questions. He observed that Chinese artists have their own philosophy and refused to adapt to the western naturalistic perspective methodology. This eastern-centric approach is totally different from the western-centric approach of seeing. Thus Piyadasa questioned; 'Why did the Chinese artists refuse to halt reality in single instance in time?' It will seem like the question seeks to belittle the Chinese artists but it is actually a paradoxical statement made to provoke the audience. To me that was not disrespect but a sincere sharing of knowledge.

c. Data collection method

Keywords: review-oriented – implementation (social)

Suggested statements:

Piyadasa reviewed Chinese art and western modern art approaches in order to understand the in-between concepts, as exemplified here by the painted black and white chair. Painted and reflected shadows led audiences into the discussion of reality and time. And the juxtaposition of objects and statement aptly demonstrates the concept of yin and yang.

d. Mode of making

Keywords: creator-centred – reinvention (vision)

Suggested statements:

It is a continuous effort best seen as an extension of the Mystical Reality manifesto. Piyadasa attempted to share his thoughts through this construction of conceptual framework.

Piyadasa's chair reflects his interest in the discovery of art making. As such it is referred to as creator-centred of art making.

e. Audience perceiving method

Keywords: cognitivism – comprehension (love)

Suggested statements:

Piyadasa's chair invited the audience to observe and go around the installation in 360 degrees.

The printed statement is the clue of the whole concept as mentioned above. (Sabapathy 2001)

(Piyadasa 1977)

4.6.2.3 Ai Weiwei's Chairs

(Ai Weiwei's *Fairytale-1001 Qing Dynasty Wooden Chairs* was part of his Fairytale (童话) series in Documenta 12. Therefore below reading referred the intertextuality of two other works entitled, *Templates* and *Fairytale-1001 Chinese Visitors*.)

a. Areas of studies

Keywords: Science and The Arts - reinvention (vision)

Suggested statements:

Ai Weiwei's *Fairytale-1001 Qing Dynasty Wooden Chairs* was a series of collectable Qing Dynasty chairs he found. Ai registered his silent protest about democracy issues with covert references to the Tiananmen Square protest; as Ai said, "Today's China is so variegated and immersed in such a restless social, historical and material dismantling/building, amnesia-inducing activity that sometimes even those who live here can have the impression that reality and fairytale melt together" (Colonnello 2007) The notion of "Fairytale"; (1) refers to unbelievable traveling experiences of 1001 Chinese visitors which was created by him; (2) refers to unbelievable experiences as the audiences of Documenta 12 listened to and witnessed Ai's "living" installation – 1001 Chinese visitors. Ai has created a dream for those selected Chinese Visitors.

b. Presentation approach

Keywords: conceptual approach- creation (belief)

Suggested statements:

Ai's 1001 chairs were scattered around the showroom of Documenta 12 randomly to invite the audience to sit on the Qing Dynasty chairs. (1) Ai's 1001 chairs represented the large demography of China. (2) The chairs had been well strategized and preserved in its original appearance to depict the western domination of global media responding to the issue of autonomy and freedom in the Chinese media. This can be traced if a western visitor (Western media capitalist) "sits" on a Qing Dynasty antique chair (China media) and thus "replacing"

the chair. One might ask, “what if one of the *China Visitors* “sits” on the Qing Dynasty antique chair?” (3) Ai’s 1001 chairs had brought the phenomenal and ambient qualities of China’s heritage through well preserved Qing Dynasty antique chairs. It is synonymous to Ai Weiwei “brought” the phenomenon and environ of Beijing through the 1001 chairs, 1001 China visitors and 1001 pieces of Qing Dynasty wooden windows panels to Documental 12 in Kessel. (Colonnello 2007)

c. Data collection method

Keywords: research-oriented - implementation (social)

Suggested statements:

“The point is: how to make everybody feel that all this is made for him or her, for each individual, and to enable the participants have a very detailed and carefully planned trip that is free? How to make sure that they have the absolutely correct conditions for traveling and being in this Documenta as viewers and at the same time as part of the work? I see the whole process as the work itself”; quoted from Ai interview. (Colonnello 2007)

(d) Mode of making

Keywords: audience & creator centred – creation (belief)

Suggested statements:

Ai interpreted the cultural and political factors of China and brilliantly strategized the curatorial of the showcase. He had interpreted the idea of Fairytale well and presented it in the combination of 1001 Qing Dynasty Chairs, 1001 Chinese Visitors and 1001 pieces of antique windows panels. As he mentioned in his interview, “Yes, there will be seats there, people can sit around... To me, events such as Documenta or *Fairytale* are like temples...” (Colonnello 2007)

(e) Audiences perceiving method

Keywords: behaviourism – implementation (social)

Suggested statements:

Ai invited audience to sit on his collected antique chairs. The notion of chairs was interpreted as a seat for contemplation. The chair setting offers the audience to contemplate and through it realise the emptiness of one's soul. As Ai referred it to as "temple"; meaning the tradition of Chinese civilisation.

4.6.2.4 *White-wooden-chair*

a. Areas of studies

Keywords: The Arts - reinvention (vision)

Suggested statements:

With the concept of "*White-wooden-chair* dreamed to be a tree". It is a metaphor of my returning to the campus that trained me as an artist. The *White-wooden-chair* (WWC) project speaks for sustainability development campaign. On the other hand, unconsciously it serves as a channel for me to voice my unconscious thoughts. It articulates (in a non-verbal way) and speaks of my personal responds to the current campus environment.

b. Presentation approach

Keywords: conceptual approach- reinvention (vision)

Suggested statements:

I am deeply interested and focussed to study audience's interaction toward an artwork or exhibits. This interaction/experience refers to the art making and the artwork; and also refers to the artwork and the audiences. It has the potential to be a platform for me to venture into study of the psychology of my own sublimity.

c. Data collection method

Keywords: research-oriented - implementation (social)

Suggested statements:

I have adapted an action research methodology as the ground for collecting audience's reaction. Unconsciously, I perform as the audience and practice interaction toward the chair. To this end, I have re-strategized my approach to adapt semiotic and critical theory studies on my findings. Quoted from Hasnul, "The 'data' on audience-interaction can be approached like a dry scientific finding. What is more interesting is the way in which the 'dialogues' and 'discourses' between you, the chair and the audience have taken place...?"ⁱⁱⁱ

(d) Mode of making

Keywords: audience/creator centred - implementation (social)

Suggested statements:

White-wooden-chair project is an engagement of the public. It is strategically installed in the middle of the student square. By it I hope to attract the most engagements and personal interactions/experience from the public. It is by nature an audience-centred public art project. As such the actions and reactions from the public serve to potentially enrich behaviourist data from studio practice perspective.

(e) Audiences perceiving method

Keywords: behaviourism - reinvention (vision)

Suggested statements:

The audience is invited to interact with the chair. The photograph documentation showed most of the audiences posed in front of the chair though some of them actually sat on it. And there is another group of photographs showing vehicles parked beside the chair; the chair being removed for official occasions and some the designed parts of the chair being broken in the process. The White-wooden-chair project is actually against museum practice in that it invites the audience to physically interact with the chair.

ⁱ *Visual Sampling Method* is invented by Assoc. Prof. Hasnul Jamal Saidon and Liew Ting Chuang since 2008, under Tuanku Fauziah Museum & Gallery (MGTF), Universiti Sains Malaysia. Currently *Visual Sampling Method (VSM) 3.0* is developing and potentially it has the means to unveil curatorial frame work, exhibition design and thematic study of an exhibition. *VSM 3.0* is expanded from its previous versions such as; *VSM 1.0* was used experimentally with fine art collection by a prominent private collector. *VSM 2.0* is an improved version and was used experimentally in Syed Ahmad Jamal (SAJ)'s retrospective (2009) to generate statistic data of SAJ's institutional collection. *Grafix In Reality* (2010) by a group of Penang emerging artists called the *Third-Eyes* adapted *VSM 2.0* to summarise their artworks into barcode-like patterns. Instead of reading in essay form, the patterns provided artworks information through info-graphic.

ⁱⁱ Read Hasnul's **Under-deconstruction: Contemporary Art in Malaysia After 1990**, in *Susurmasa*, National Art Gallery, 2008, pp 256. Hasnul stated in his essay, In Malaysia, the term 'issues based art' (IBA) has been coined to explain artworks with more pronounced political and social concerns. Cited from chapter on 'Issues based art' in Syed Ahmad Jamal (ed), *The Encyclopedia of Malaysia: Crafts and The Visual Arts*, Didier Millet, Singapore, 2007, pp. 118-119.

ⁱⁱⁱ Quoted from Facebook's closed group, entitled What the Hack? (WTH). A group of artists/art students from Malaysian Art scene forming a platform for meaningful intellectual discourse. (accessed on 7 November 2010)

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Chapter 5: *White-wooden-chair* extended the friendship (Implementation)

(This chapter reviews the interaction from the audience, the School of The Arts and my response; bringing the “model” into practice. It is partly adopted from unpublished writing assignment entitled, *Simply a Flash of Mind – Gift from the Universe*, written in December 2010)

Figure 28: How fast do the Rain-drops fall?

5.1 Crossing the green culture

White-wooden-chair extended his friendship to meet more friends. It has invited all the members from different layers of society to pay a visit. It wished to make dialogue among the visitors and listen to the members of nature. The silent voices from them; how are Busy-ants work, why do Trendy-mosquitoes drink bloods, how do Cheerful-birds sing, where are Dry-leaves flow, how fast do the Rain-drops fall, when are Dry-branches fall, when is Reflected-shadow appear, how long do the Growing-trees live and how strong does the Blowing-wind flow. Let's the public will learn more about the *White-wooden-chair*.

(Written in September 2010)

One might ask, “Who are the audience?”

All the members of the campus are the audience of *White-wooden-chair* project; where I have grouped them into three main categories, such as the first-person, the second-person and the third-person audience; which adopted from my presented paper as below.

“I decided to conduct an audience-participant project which employed drawing as a mediator to collect visual data through mark-making and as ‘props’. A site-specific installation is required to build up the mood and environment, as a ‘**stage**’ for public performance; whereby I was performing as ‘the artist’ (**the first-person**) and the participant was performing as the ‘local community’ (**the second-person**). **The third-person** or the participant’s friends witness the ‘performance art’ which was happening inside the glass wall partition room”; quoted from my research paper entitled, *Meeting the South: Dialogues-through-drawings (2009): Generating Behaviourist Data through Drawings*, (2011)ⁱ

Hence, in *White-wooden-chair* project **the first-person** is synonym to me (the artist); **the second-person** is synonym to members of the School of The Arts; and **the third-person** is synonym to other members of the campus or the audience. The notion of “**stage**” refers to the surrounding of *Permatang Pelajar* - student square of Universiti Sains Malaysia. (See Figure 15 & 16 at Chapter 4) The argument of “first and the third person” further describes the concept of interaction/experience.

5.2 I have played as “The-first-person” in *White-wooden-chair*.

Quoted from Hasnul’sⁱⁱ comment, “The ‘data’ on audience-interaction can be approached like a dry scientific finding. What is more interesting is the way in which the ‘dialogues’ and ‘discourses’ between you, the chair and the audience have taken place...?”ⁱⁱⁱ

5.2.1 I have low ability in writing.

I have low ability in writing. Being handicapped as such I was unable to contextualise the “future” of the working progress. The bottom line is, I could not precisely forecast and plan the making of artworks that I was going to do. I have always believed that it serves no purpose to discuss an idea without any concrete action being taken. The unconscious and spontaneous play an important part of my art making because it potentially leads to others possibility of the outcome. This was what happened in the 4th week of the semester (end of July 2010), while I was in the process of visualising my artworks entitled *The Returning - Silent Dialogue* (2010-2011) (Ting Chuang, *The Returning - Silent Dialogue* 2010-2011), *The Returning – Branches Out* (2010) (performance) (Ting Chuang, *The Returning - Branches Out* 2010) and *The Returning - Visual Diary* (2010) (see Figure 20) (Ting Chuang, *The Returning - Visual Diary* 2010).

Those have exhibited at *Galeri Dua Puluh Tujuh, Universiti Sains Malaysia* for *The “Making” Archive^{iv}*, MA studio showcase.

Several writing assignments were requested by the lecturers on the different topics, such as the role of an artist, past and future issues in the art making, argument of originality and concept of aesthetics. I have intentionally compressed the requested essays in single bigger one

Figure 29: *The Returning - Visual Diary* (2010) at *Galeri Dua Puluh Tujuh, USM*.

for a more comprehensive reading. I encountered many difficulties in summarising and trying to arrive at a conclusion in my art making, putting them into texts while the works were in progress. It took about three months to complete the artworks (partially); and a further two weeks to conceptualise the MA showcase. In hindsight I see that the problem arose in tandem with my transition from the “cross-road” to the path of improvement into academia.

I have written three essays within the semester (July – November 2010), taking it as a challenge to put into words the whole body of the curatorial for writing exercises sake; for me, it was an attempt to turn the studio making practices into writing momentum. The essays are listed as below:

5.2.1.1 *Making Archive – Archiving the Making (Part 1)*, curatorial statements.

5.2.1.2 *Making Archive – Archive the Making (Part 2)*, brief introduction of Visual Sampling Method Version 3.0.

5.2.1.3 *Thirst by Izumi Ueda Yuu* – introduction for Izumi’s solo exhibition and published in *Thirst - Izumi Ueda Yuu* catalogue under Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah publication. (Hasnul Jamal Saidon & Liew Ting Chuang 2010)

5.2.2 Being the *Old Drunkard* in reality? (Questioning the role in fine art)

I was pondering into the issue of; what is my role as an artist; due to the fulfilment for the requested writing assignments. I was embracing myself; being the *Old Drunkard* in the *White-wooden-chair* project?

醉翁之意不在酒，在乎山水之间也。宋·欧阳修《醉翁亭记》 (He gave himself the sobriquet of the Old Drunkard. But it was not wine that attracted him to this spot; it was

the charming scenery which “wine” enable him to enjoy. (Ow-yang Hein, in *The Old Drunkard’s Arbour*, 1045 Soong Dynasty) (Giles, 2007)

I found problems when it comes to conclude my role being an “artist”. The keyword, “artist” is at once controversial and abstract, it is understood differently by different layers of society. It could be interpreted as craftsman, painters, sculptors, performers, singers, comedians and et cetera, which are indeed all professions in the arts.

5.2.3 Re-questioned myself about the role of an “artist”.

In 2007, we had a discussion about the difference between an artist and a designer in *Design Theory* class, conducted by Associate Professor A. Rahman Mohamed. We were discussing about the 70’s monumental sculpture in USM, which is located in one of the roundabouts. The specimen is posted in the class to show the different role between a designer and an artist. Rahman mentioned that the artist’s creation is less a work of art than a consideration of functionality and accessibility.

I disagreed with him because the sculpture has a symbolical function that touches the audience’s spirit and emotion in the context of phenomenology. Nuzul^v further discussed this in his essay, touching upon the *revocative turn*, (Manen 1999) which the artwork revoking the meaning is assigned to them, to return to the experience before. I shared from “artist” perspective, and opined that it was not appropriate to say “less functionality and accessibility” in a scholarly discussion.

Rahman replied, “Who endorse you as an “artist”? “The dialogue ended unfavourably with both sides trying to portray own ego. (Judith, Sacred Centers, 2002) After the incident, I re-questioned myself about the role of an “artist” in the contexts of contemporary society.

5.2.4 Touching my *Chakra Two: Svadhisthana*.

I was invited to give a talk at *Neo-Art Institute* in Johor Baharu, last March 2009. I shared my artworks chronologically from 1999 till 2008, which are my early works and the *[tan-jong i-tuo bi-kin] Made in Penang* series (2007-2008). It was more like story-telling; the audience enjoyed the talk very much. I concluded the talk with my art making methodology. (See Figure 4 at Chapter 2)

At the end of the talk, Mr. Lok Chi Wah, the principle of *Neo-art Institute* commended me. He said in Mandarin, (家 means expert or who is specialising in certain area)^{vi} that I am multitalented, being a picture-making expert (画家 painter), design expert (设计家 designer), theory expert (理论家 theorist), philosophy expert (哲学家 philosopher), and architecture and interior design expert (建筑学家 architect). He asked me if there were any others profession that he had forgotten to mention. I simply replied, 穷人家 (bagger).

Although I appreciated Lok's words I felt uncomfortable. My reply might sound sarcastic to others but at that moment I was jobless and poor. The experience veiled the role of an "artist" from the reality of the economic point of view. My artworks did not help me make a living. The experience touched my *Chakra Two: Svadhisthana*, which is desire. (Judith, *Sacred Centers*, 2002) After the incident, I questioned myself about the role of an "artist" again, am I making art for the purpose of earning money and living?

5.2.5 To exploring the notion of interaction/experience.

Civilization is the catalyst of art production. I have kept on imitating, experiencing, comprehending, and re-inventing; any happenings around me affected me. I would like to say,

my current role is as a postgraduate student in Fine Art, at The School of the Arts, Universiti Sains Malaysia.

5.3 The members of the School of The Arts have played as “The-second-person”.

Members of the school had played an import role here to respond to *White-wooden-chair*; where they had shared their opinions on *White-wooden-chair* from their perspectives.

5.3.1 Mat Desa Mat Rodzi’s comments from educational point of views.

I have submitted the conceptual review^{vii} of *White-wooden-chair* to Mat Desa Mat Rodzi for a preliminary idea about my current role of art making. He commented that *White-wooden-chair* functions as a piece for educational purposes. *White-wooden-chair* was a public installation at the student square in Universiti Sains Malaysia. It is located right in front of the School of the Arts. *White-wooden-chair* is a model designed for collecting audiences’ interactions through participation to study about audience behaviour. It was scheduled to run from 1 September till 31 December 2010. *White-wooden-chair* has “played” many functions in the project as I have discussed at Chapter 4, it is more than a piece of installation.

5.3.2 Questioning of originality from Mohammad Khizal Mohamed Saat

Discussions and polemics about "originality" took place in the 70’s not “now”. In the current stage, the question of originality is not an issue in local art scene. Contemporary art

scene is more than able to provide a platform for discussion from multiple perspectives with viewpoints from sociology, economy, culture, identity et cetera.

It reminded me of Piyadasa and Suleiman's *Mystical Concept of Time and Event* manifesto (Redza Piyadasa, Suleiman Esa 1974). The manifesto referred to the artist's behaviourist practices that are treated as a form of meditation for those who believe in Zen practice or a Minimalism approach in western terminology; which Piyadasa and Suleiman referred to as an "event". Their undertaking can be interpreted as an act of enhancement of Kosuth's theory.

Piyadasa and Suleimen's effort was the beginning of celebrating the conceptual approach in local art history whereby they looked into local contexts and escaped from "humanistic-subjection". (Jit 1974) In 1983, Piya and Sabapathy expanded and experimented a similar concept in a research that profile Modern Malaysian artists. It was then published as the earlier version of artist directory by Universiti Sains Malaysia, entitled *Modern Artists of Malaysia*. (Sabapathy 1983) The review was based on historical and psychological factors by ignoring formalistic and stylistic references as fundamentals. Many years after that, a lot of controversy arose due to misreading the preface section of their publication. It was their disclaimer reminding readers that the research outcome was experimental and hypothetical in nature and this invited more researchers to share their approach.

Browsing through the 307 pages *Susurmasa* (Susurmasa - Timelines, 2008), a National Art Gallery Malaysia's (NAG) collaborative publication; one encounter a vivid and comprehensive collection of seminal artworks from NAG collections, inspiring and awakening. What makes these artworks important in the national art collection?

Assoc. Prof. Hasnul Jamal Saidon leads his readers into the prelude of Malaysia contemporary art before 1990 in his article published in *Susurmasa*. (Hasnul Jamal, Under-

deconstruction: Contemporary Art in Malaysia after 1990 2008) He reviewed past publications by T.K. Sabapathy's early effort in archiving Malaysia art development. Part of the review include Redza Piyadasa's concept of Malay 'root' and 'Malay-Islamic revival', Suleimen Esa's Malaysian perspective of Islamic art, Joseph Tan's commentary of Young Contemporary 2000 selected entries, Michelle Antoinette's overall review of Malaysian Art in 1990s, Dr. Tan Chee Khuan's argument to defend Yong Mun Seng as the 'father of Malaysian Painting', Ooi Kok Chuen's 'syiok' a pun commentary about local artists encountering globalisation, Jolly Koh's pin-pointed misconceptions in art writing, Lee Kian Seng's mandarin newspaper reviews of his personal development in art, Ahmad Suhaimi Mohd.'s thesis about the compilation of Malayan visual culture. June Yap quoted Piyadasa's statement on Malay revivalist proclivities as well as Wong Hoy Cheong's statement on figurative representation issue in UiTM, Ahmad Mashadi's quoted Wong Hoy Cheong's statement on young ITM graduates rebellion to assert their presence into mainstream art by painting figurative. There were many others such as J. Anu, Niranjan Rajah, Valentine Willie & Karim Raslan, Suzieana Uda Nagu, Ismail Zain and Jailani Abu Hassan. (Can read as the commentaries on how the local 1990's artists searching for "originalities" of their making.)

These commentaries and reviews by the heavyweights (Piyadasa, Suleiman, Sabapathy and Hasnul), serve as a reflection about the roots of Malaysia Art which is structured by diversity of cultural backgrounds. In understanding our background and roots, it is important to nurture the belief of individuality in art making which best fit one's own style. The concept of originality can be easily traced from one's creation. Since 1974 until 2008, the contributors or these "Old Drunkards" (in my terminology) gave clues to all of us who are involved in the local art scene, so that we will be enlightened in building "originality" in our creation. Assoc. Prof. Hasnul shared in What The Hack? (a closed group forum), "Instead of writing as means of justifying, why not as means of unveiling."^{viii}

5.3.3 Contradiction of “aesthetics” in contemporary practices, an enquiry by Shahrul Anuar Shaari.

However, in Graduate Seminar class we are still invited to discuss concepts of "originality" and "aesthetics" in traditional philosophy contexts. The question is how we able to expand the argument into advancement or based on our current studio practice?

Other questions were posted, mainly on the issues of aesthetic value, as an effort to stimulate further discussion as showcased in *Absorbing Future Shock* (AFS) (2010) which was exhibited at Adiwana Gallery, School of the Arts, USM. It would seem, based on the response that it is impossible to lead discussions into this stage. In the simplest way of saying, everyday you make your choice of seeing, giving perception and opinion; another word to say, you choose with your sense of aesthetic.

"Contemporary Art Campus (CAC) is also an important part of MGTF's research project on USM Fine Art Collection. It allows MGTF to gain pertinent data on accessibility, public engagement and enrichment of interpretation, alternative curatorial strategy, exhibition management, branding and audience development." – Assoc. Prof. Hasnul Jamal Saidon.

In short, ASF is a compression of experimental, conceptual and new media artworks from varied contemporary artists which responds towards technological intervention and existentialist's interpretation of self, identity and representation of global telecommunication and industrial mechanisation. (Hasnul Jamal, Contemporary Art Campus-Absorbing Future Shock: Video, Digital & New Media Art 2010) ASF is designed for a multi-layered society and it has been toned down to fit audience's taste. The core objective and message can be easily channelled to the public for educational purposes, social problem awareness and as a reflection of life. To delve fully into the arguments and theories, a few works come to mind as basic required reading list:

5.3.3.1 *Cabaran Praktis Seni Elektronik Dalam Era Maklumat* (Hasnul Jamal, Cabaran Praktis Seni Elektronik dalam Era Maklumat 2003)

- To equip fundamental knowledge of the development of new media culture.

5.3.3.2 *Under-deconstruction: Contemporary Art in Malaysia after 1990* (Hasnul Jamal, Under-deconstruction: Contemporary Art in Malaysia after 1990 2008)

- To understand contemporary change in local art scene.

5.3.3.3 *Bridge to the Future - 7 keys* (Judith 2002)

- To fluid human being egoistic so that learn acceptance from the surrounding.

“Since the Buddha first preached compassion 2600 years ago, and Christ (and other form of higher power as we refer as God) taught us to love our neighbour as ourselves, there has been a gradual – in fact very gradual – awakening of concern for the rights of others.” – Anodea Judith.

5.3.4 In between of “Red and the Blue Ocean”

The location of installation is full of greenery, a natural environment ideally suited for student programmes and activities. Vehicles and motorists were barred from that particular area but it is a requisite that was hard to enforce by the management of the university. Occasional conflicts happened, but the School of The Arts stayed neutral in this problem. As

it turned out, the installation was removed without advanced early notification. The project ended earlier than had been scheduled, while the MA showcase was still going on.

The School of The Arts is heading towards a “boutique art school” concept^{ix}. If take further step to investigate the strategy of “boutique art school” in sustainable development term; the School of The Arts is pushing its uniqueness or peaking into its niches with the sense of luxuriousness and exclusivity in marketing approaches within the “Red Ocean” of traditional studio-based art instructions. Rahman has adopted SWOT analysis where the art school are; **strengths** – the oldest Fine Art programme in Bachelor degree in local higher institution; **weaknesses** - lack of professional in most of the existing areas, **opportunities** - potential of integration of art and technology in developing industry, and **threats** - challenges from well-established art school. The analysis shows the school is into industry-driven and defending the legacy of Dr. Chew Tian Beng (alternative print-making – paper making) or in the “Red Ocean” phenomenal. (W. Chan Kim, Renee Mauborge, 刘华才 (translated) 2007)

The school is moving toward specialisation in relief printing and “banana trunk fibre” paper making for the establishment of “boutique art school”; where these particular areas have its potential into crafts, tourism and commercialisation. From my point of view, the “boutique art school” concept is in the “Red Ocean” phenomenal because Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) has long history in studio based art instructions and research in several areas as such, Painting (Assoc. Prof. Jailani Abu Hassan), Sculpture (Assoc. Prof. Ramlan Abdullah) & Print-making (Assoc. Prof. Ponirin Amin); who are leading in current fine art industry in Malaysia. (as well as in crafts, tourism and commercialisation). UiTM has trained many leading artists in local art scene. (Hasnul Jamal 2011) (UiTM 2009)

It is leading us to the question posted by Professor James Elkins; *Is contemporary art instruction academic?* According to Prof. Elkins, most of the global academic pertains to the

successors and imitators of earlier styles neither contemporary instruction nor avant-garde. The phenomenon leads to time lag between contemporary practice and 'academic'; or practicing art making and teaching art. This instruction scenario somewhat fits to Prof. Elkins's reviews. He wrote in his book that formularised art teaching (like that practiced by the Carracci academy; in short "eclectic") easily influences students to imitate the forms and subjects of popular culture, but their strategies derived largely from the European and American masters. Locally, it might derive from the "Mixed Media" trend (which is emphasised on skills and techniques; doesn't similar to Expanded Media – studio-based conceptual exploration) which is celebrated by most art institutions, contemporary practitioners, art patrons and local institutions. In this form, the role of thinking in the making and appreciation of art is lost. (Elkins, *Conversations* 2001) For example, Van Gogh did his mixing on the canvas spontaneously; indirectly this unique methodology became his style and treatment. For Van Gogh, this was his abstraction of making. If a student imitated Van Gogh's style, it is not considered as his (the student's) abstraction; but just merely an imitation. Abstraction is a state of mind. No one can replace someone else's mindscape, it is unique.

Even though Professor Tan Sri Dato' Dzulkipli Abd Razak has mentioned, "Not competing head-on (existing competitions) but competing in the area you think you are not relevant (potential uncontested area)" (Dzulkipli 2008) School of The Arts, Universiti Sains Malaysia has others developing and undeveloped niches; namely Expanded Painting (Assoc. Prof. Fauzan Omar), Electronic Art/New Media Art, art curatorial design and art inventory research - Visual Sampling Method (Assoc. Prof. Hasnul Jamal Saidon), natural sources colour pigments (Shamsu Muhamad), mass media advertising and creative copywriting (Alias Ibrahim), critical theories and art writing (Dr. Izmer Ahmad) and others areas in music and theatre. Above phenomenal part and partial influenced the *White-wooden-chair* project.

5.4 Audience as the “The-third-person”.

Figure 30 shown students' activities in front of the main office of School of The Arts.

5.4.1 Statistic of *White-wooden-chair*'s audience.

I have conducted simple questionnaire survey for the first month of installation, where *White-wooden-chair* was exhibited as part of *Absorbing Future Shock* (AFS) (2010), in Malaysia Contemporary Art Tourism (MCAT) Penang Chapter 2010. Further the similar survey done in the last month of the installation; *White-wooden-chair* was exhibited in *The “Making” Archive* (2010) at the Gallery *Dua Puluh Tujuh*; the MA showcase was included as one of the field trip sites for University Museum Network International Conferences 2010 which held at Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah, Universiti Sains Malaysia.

The questionnaire is adopted simple graphic forms to show the actions of how audience respond to the chair. (Figure 23) There are six options of respond; mainly it can break down into two major categories based on *Learning Style Inventory* (Kolb 1981), as basic framework. The first category includes; sitting (RO+CE+CE), sitting backward (AE+CE) and squatting on chair (AC+AE+AE); which touch the function of rear cortex (concrete experience - CE), archived 51 % of 121 respondents. Next the second category shows 47% in pie chart, accumulated from standing (RO+RO+CE), passing by (AC+RO) and squatting (nearby) (AC+AC+AE); touch the function of frontal cortex (abstract conceptualisation - AC) (Figure 24)

Figure 31: How do you pose in front of White-wooden-chair? (Survey sheet)

White-wooden-chair audience reactions (N=121)

Figure 32 shown *White-wooden-chair* audience reactions (N = 121)

Most of the *White-wooden-chair*'s audience has chosen "sitting" to describe their interaction; these archived 31%; 37 of 121 audiences. "Standing" is the second highest selections, 21% is equivalent to 25 audiences. The result has shown, the installation of *White-wooden-chair* has it potential to invite audiences to sit on it. The statistic is shown 50% of audiences (61 audiences who sat, sat (backward) and squatted on the chair) slightly higher than who chose to observe (57%, N=47) in certain distances.

I have further investigates the different between ages group in three categories; teenagers (12 – 20 years old), adults (21 – 49 years old) and senior adults (50 years old above). The result has shown in charts as below.

Figure 33: White-wooden-chair's audiences - teenagers (N = 27)

Figure 34: White-wooden-chair's audiences - adults (N = 81)

Figure 35: *White-wooden-chair's* audiences - senior adults (N = 13)

Figures 33, 34 and 35 have shown contrast different between age groups. Figure 33 shows 30% of teenagers chose to try on “sitting” on the *White-wooden-chair*. Additionally Figure 33 shows 19% of teenagers chose “sitting (backward)” option. According to theory, the pattern indicates most of the teenagers have engaged to the installation with their feeling.

Figure 34 shows “sitting” 31%, “standing” 21% and “passing by” 21%; at the conclusion, the theory indicates that most of the adults choose to observe, feel and think; to demonstrate their interaction to *White-wooden-chair*.

Figure 35 shows the obvious result; where senior adults demonstrated accommodator’s characteristic in the interaction to *White-wooden-chair*. Senior adult choose to learn from “hand-on” experience as assume the interaction like taking new challenging

experiences. They may be to act on “gut” feelings rather than on logical analysis. (David A. Kolb, Richard E. Boyatzis, Charalampos Mainemelis 1999)

5.4.2 白木椅 (bai-mu-yee) or *White-wooden-chair* in Facebook.com

Figure 36: Screenshot of 白木椅 (bai-mu-yee) or *White-wooden-chair* in Facebook.com

Instead of knowing the audience through physical interaction, I have expanded the interaction through cyberspace. For the sake of catalyst interacting engagement, I have created a Facebook account for *White-wooden-chair* to anthropomorphise it into 50 years old women. I have named it as 白木椅 (bai-mu-yee) which is the direct translation of *White-wooden-chair*.

白木椅 has introduced herself as 50 years old wooden chair originally was in black but now it prefer to fashion herself in white-colour appearance. She likes to be call as “White-wooden-chair”. She feels lonely in the studio where surrounded by four white panel walls. The *White-wooden-chair* wishes to return to Mother Nature as what she was in the original form. 白木椅’s Facebook profile photography displayed her tree-chair silhouettes on pink polka-dots

Figure 37: The pinky-polka-dot icon of 白木椅 (bai-mu-yee).

background as shown in Figure 29. Therefore all the respond from 白木椅 Facebook’s account will display the pinky-polka-dot icon and remarked as 白木椅, in Chinese characters.

Figure 38 has shown drawn instruction at the installation site.

Audiences are invited to post their candid photographs at specific Facebook group, entitled *White-wooden-chair* group. Figure 30 has shown drawn instruction at the installation site. Quantifying the audiences respond in statistic has shown interesting result and conclusion. I have taken further step to pondering into more meaningful and humanistic interaction/experience therefore the *White-wooden-chair* group has created for that purpose.

White-wooden-chair Facebook.com group.

URL: <http://www.facebook.com/group.php?gid=146525152053730>

Figure 39: Screenshot of White-wooden-chair Facebook.com group

ⁱ Research paper entitled, *Meeting the South: Dialogues-through-drawings (2009): Generating Behaviourist Data through Drawings*, presented in *The 2nd Performing Arts as Creative Industries in Asia (PACIA) 2011 – Convergence in Performing & Creative Arts*, School of The Arts, Universiti Sains Malaysia.

ⁱⁱ **Associate Professor Hasnul Jamal Saidon** is currently expanding his frequencies into the domain of obscured dwellers in the vicinity of Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Penang, under the pretext of his current position as the Director of the Museum. Hasnul is the **advisor for White-wooden-chair project** for the fulfillment of Master of Arts (Visual Art and Design), mixed mode programme by the School of The Arts, Universiti Sains Malaysia.

ⁱⁱⁱ Quoted from Facebook's closed group, entitled *What the Hack? (WTH)*. A group of artists/art students from Malaysian Art scene forming a platform for meaningful intellectual discourse. (accessed on 7 November 2010)

^{iv} *The "Making" Archive* is opened to public from 1 November till 31 December 2010. URL: <http://www.facebook.com/album.php?aid=243798&id=631086934&l=19c22d6cec> (Retrieved on 29 November 2010)

^v *Nuzul Haqimi Mohammad*, one of the member of MA studio 2010/2011. He is researching about the concept of phenomenology in perspective of architecture. His research elaborates on *Phenomenological Inquiry Model* (van Manen, 2002) relating to his installation entitled, *Parallax Error* (2010) which is included in *The "Making" Archive* (2010). His essay, *Adopting Phenomenological Inquiry Model in Art (Making, Interpretation or Appreciation)*, posted at *What the Heck?* at Facebook closed group discussion. URL: http://www.facebook.com/note.php?note_id=160215294014037

^{vi} Further reading about 家 URL: <http://www.nciku.com/search/zh/detail/%E5%AE%B6/1307102> (Retrieved on 1 December 2010)

^{vii} For further reading for **Conceptual Review** of *White-wooden-chair* project, URL: <http://www.facebook.com/topic.php?uid=146525152053730&topic=447> (Retrieved on 1 December 2010)

^{viii} Quoted from the comments of earlier version notes on Facebook closed group. (Retrieved on 4 December 2010)

^{ix} Associate Professor A. Rahman Haji Mohamed, the Dean of School of The Arts shared his prospect of the School of The Arts in informal meeting after his studio visit, early of September 2010. As Rahman mentioned, the school is looking potential lecturer like Associate Professor Jailani Abu Hassan who is active in academic and art industry. Rahman is adopted SWOT analysis to help him to analyst the potential of the school and making it toward "**boutique art school**" actualisation.

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Chapter 6: White-wooden-chair actualised its (my) dream (reinvention)

(This chapter reported the result of the curatorial process of Master of Arts [Visual Art & Design] Thesis Exhibition and Research Outcome Exhibition by the rest of the studio members. The curatorial strategy is derived from the experimented theories and methodology where I have brought it into a deeper level. I have excerpted few writings from; *White-wooden-chair* synopsis for *Signature Art Prize 2011* nomination, email interview transcript for *1001 Malaysian Artists 1 Malaysia* and the curatorial essay of MA thesis exhibition to portray the outcome of this MA research.)

White-wooden-chair Facebook group extends the interaction of ‘nature’ dialogue into the World Wide Web (WWW), therefore *White-wooden-chair* expands its friendship to the members of nature such as the *Busy-ants*, the *Trendy-mosquitoes*, the *Cheerful-birds*, the *Dry-leaves*, the *Rain-drops*, the *Dry-branches*, the *Reflected-shadow*, the *Growing-trees*, the *Blowing-wind* and the members of society as well. It plays the role as nature ambassador.

The tree-like shadow triggers the curiosity of the public. A hidden camera is installed into the chair to capture the spontaneous response of the public. The real-time video is projected onto a wall with a tree-like silhouette. Juxtaposition of the artificial tree shadow and projected participants’ image showcases the performance between *White-Wooden-Chair* and the participants, highlighting the “performative” quality of it. (Wikipedia 2011)

The *White-wooden-chair* project crosses over the public installation space, into the virtual space and then projected into the gallery space. This thematically and conceptually discusses the notion of reality in the physical and virtual world. There is an importance between humanly constructed reality and human-independent reality. (Rusbult 2003)

(Written on 30 March 2011)

Figure 40: Artist impression for *Signature Art Prize 2011*

6.1 Defining “what I have done” for MA research.

This section I have excerpted email interview transcript from *1001 Malaysian Artists 1Malaysia* because throughout the years I was facing difficulty to explain my art making to the members of the public. This MA research partly helps me searching for the meaning of art making as inserted at below.

6.1.1 E-mail interview questions from 1001Malaysian Artists 1Malaysia.

(Replied on 15 January 2011)

6.1.1.1 What year did you start painting full-time?

Since 2005, I have been actively involved in the local art exhibitions. That was after I quit from my job as graphic designer; enrolled to School of The Arts, Universiti Sains Malaysia for studying Fine Art.

6.1.1.2 What genre of art do you paint?

I work in cross-media, which includes drawing, painting, photography, print, site-specific installation, video and performance. Therefore I prefer to interpret the concept of “to paint” as making artwork. I consider art making is ongoing study of “interaction/experience” that invites audience to participate; it is focusing on interactivity as an event to convey, indicate, depict, describe, perform and express to others. I treat the body of work as “research model”. On the other hand, the interaction of audience is the soul of my artworks and leading me to shift into “information art”.

6.1.1.3 What is your favourite or trademark subject?

Most of my artworks touch on cultural commentary, as a channel to understand and learns about my root and family tradition. On conceptual level, my artworks unveil the behaviour of audience participation of my artworks. Therefore the behaviourist data or information is my favourite subjects.

6.1.1.4 Why did you choose to paint (make artworks on) this subject and what is the message you'd like to convey to the viewer?

I invite audience to comprehend my artworks through physical interaction. Basically physical touch is allow, that I referred that as “interaction/experience”. Therefore I share my visual and emotional experiences through simulacrum (simulated environments). Audience not only see but they “learn” my experiences.

6.1.1.5 Tell us more about your artistic process; what tools and mediums do you use and what is your source of inspiration?

Civilization is the catalyst of art production. I've keep on imitating, experiencing, comprehending, and re-inventing; the universe is the mentor of life. Life is exquisite inspiration. I have habit of collecting unique junks or artefacts. It reflects the fetishism manner because I believe that collecting and retouching process able to rejuvenate my “emotional sick”. Readymade and found objects are my choices. On the other hand, I

like to collect data from the audience's participation. Then I diagrams the data based on designed formulas that adapted from scientific theories.

Figure 41: The real-time video is projected onto a wall with a tree-like silhouette.

6.1.1.6 What do you feel defines your artwork? What makes it unique?

I would say conceptual art and information art. Beside it fulfil the ordinary functions of arts; I have expanded the function of art as “research model” which adopted the concept of action research and it is an event to convey, indicate, depict, describe, perform and express to others.

6.1.1.7 What are your artistic influences and artists or art movements that you admire?

I was inspired by Tristan Tzara's *Lecture on Dada* (1922), Joseph Kosuth's *Art After Philosophy* (1969)

and Jean Baudrillard's *Simulacrum* (1980) to study of interactivity between audiences, as I referred as “interaction/experience”. International artist like Yoko Ono, local artists like Lee Kian Seng, Redya Piyadasa, Fauzan Omar and Hasnul Jamal Saidon are producing artworks which are fit the idea of “interaction/experience”.

6.1.1.8 What do you wish to achieve through your artworks or as a Malaysian artist?

For the convergence of arts and sciences.

6.2 Harvesting the fruit of *White-wooden-chair*

Below essay has excerpted from the curatorial essay entitled, *Silent dialogues, simply "semicolon – close parenthesis" ;)* Thesis Exhibition of Master of Arts (Visual Art and Design) 2010/11. The essay is edited by Muhammad Hanif bin Hosainel Majidi.

Figure 42: Layout plan for *Silent Dialogue, Simply Semicolon - Close Parenthesis ;)*

We hold dialogues in each moment to share the voices deep inside us. We feel and express; perceive and see; plan and decide; try out and react - suggesting the existence of dialogue. A dialogue involves two or more parties in conversation, and is featured in books, plays and films. According to the Oxford Dictionary, dialogue refers to the exploration of a particular subject or resolution of a problem. The common definition of “dialogue” is the communication channel that involves narratives and texts. But what if the notion of “dialogue” is implemented in visual art, bridging two or more artworks for “intertextuality”; the reading

of visual language gathers more information for the enhancement on the function of art. Consequently “dialogues” occur between two or more artworks without involving any texts and narratives; into the making of “silent dialogues”. (Jensen 1986)

Figure 43: *The Returning - Silent Dialogue* (Ting Chuang 2010-2011)

6.2.1 Section1: *Berdialog Dengan Kampo Harada*

Berdialog Dengan Kampo Harada (2011) is translated as “dialogues with Kampo Harada”. Currently it is being showcased at Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah (MGTF), Universiti Sains Malaysia till the middle of May. MGTF re-interprets Kampo’s “Avant-garde” calligraphy series and selected paintings from MGTF’s fine art collection by Cheong Wen Hsi, Cheong Soo Pieng, Tay Bak Koi, Yee Chin Ming, Rahime Harun and Mazli Mahali. The

Figure 44: Cheong Soo Pieng's *Ganjil (unusual)* (1965) and Kampo's *Vibrating* (1984)

showcase juxtaposes eastern calligraphy and western style painting to demonstrate formal and aesthetic qualities in different tones. For instance, Kampo's *Vibrating* (1984) and Cheong Soo Pieng's *Ganjil (unusual)* (1965) depict the equalised state of vibrations through Kampo's washed and Soo Pieng's wet-on-wet marks on papers. In contrast, Kampo's *Healthy Living* (1984) depicts the romantic and poetic life style like cranes resting on a lakeside in the spring. It is

exceptionally complimented by Rahime's *Kebebasan Terhad* (limitation of freedom) (2007) which portrays the social impact of modernisation where citizens live in compartmented pigeon holes. The comparison of Kampo's and Rahime's artworks demonstrates both positive and negative views of living. This is why *Berdialog Dengan Kampo Harada* (2011) is included in the MA thesis exhibition as part of Liew Ting Chuang's research. Ting Chuang, one of the MA candidates who adapted the concept of intertextuality traversed his studies of artists' behaviourist data to suggest multiple layers of reading or interpretation.

One might ask, "What was the artist's reaction when he/she was producing such beautiful artworks?"

Charles R. Jensen defines art as a set of interactions between the artist and his/her artworks. The powers of making decision catalyses the artist to create personalised, stylistic and expressive touches in his/her art making then further leading to abstraction. By this definition, artwork is an evidence of how people make decisions and create meanings. The database is graphically plotted, diagrammed and mapped into a chart format. It simplifies and organises the data of the complex processes of the human mind; read as a pattern of the artist's expressions, behaviours, ideas and thoughts.

The database functions as 'tools' that give meaning to a piece of artwork; in science, they can be referred to as a 'byte' – the basic computer unit which is the building block of gigantic databases; or the microtubule associated protein (MAP), the tiniest component in a human being's brain that sparks complex thoughts and ideas. (Taylor 2010)

The diagrammatic data gives information on both the micro and macro levels. In the micro level it addressed the audience with detailed information of formalistic elements. On the other hand, in the macro level audiences is able to trace the thinking and behaviourist patterns of the person behind the piece of art; perhaps in a larger picture the diagram itself showcased the thinking of the visual interpreters. (Carolyn Knight, Jessica Glaser 2009) It creates a 'neutral ground' for other curators, artists and researchers to interpret the database in varied readings or data interpretations. A comparison of the data obtained generated information within a certain perimeter which was made on the basis of related visual elements.

Figure 45: Mapping of *Silent Dialogue* (generating behaviourist data)

In figure 37, the “transparent cube-like” diagram represents a simple model of the human brain (cerebrum) which has eight sections that indicate left and right hemispheres (on z-axis); the frontal lobe (left section), parietal lobe (top section), occipital lobe (right section) and temporal lobe (bottom section) on x & y - axis are as referred to as the “neocortex”. (Zull 2002) The smaller cube which is in the middle of the structure indicates the limbic system;

the structure that catalyse gut and intuition. It triggers our reactions to fear and pleasure as well and responds to the sublime.

The z-axis adapts the *Split-brain theory* (Sperry 1975) that introduced the integration of hemispheric specialisation of human brain functions. The right hemisphere of the brain cortex excels at nonverbal and spatial tasks; it responds to one's intuitive ability. The left hemisphere of the cortex is dominant in verbal tasks like writing and speaking; it also catalyses the analytic and logical power of the brain. A list of painterly marks are categorised into two groups based on the hemispheric specialisation. For instance, staining marks has a quality of spontaneity therefore it suggests that the artist responded using the right hemisphere of the brain cortex. Hatching marks require organised and analytical attitude hence it suggests response by the left hemisphere of the brain.

The x-axis (AC - CE) and y-axis (AE - RO) adapted the *Learning Style Inventory* (LSI) (Kolb 1984, 2011) that suggests four dimensions of learning preferences, such as concrete experience (feeling) (CE), reflective observation (seeing) (RO), abstract conceptualisation (thinking) (AC) and active experimentation (doing) (AE). The LSI method assesses the response of the reaction of the human brain through calculation. If the LSI method is used in visual art, it has the potential to unveil the processes involved in the making of a piece of artwork or visual database.

6.2.2 Section 2: *Dialogue Within Physical Space*

The micro level of diagrammatic data addresses the details of formalistic information which is exhibited in Section 1: *Berdialog Dengan Kampo Harada*. Consequently, *Dialogue Within Physical Space* showcases the macro level of diagrammatic data in art making – the

behaviourist data – of the artists. This section includes series of artworks by Maizul Affendy bin Baharudin and Leila Kakaabdollah Shirazi, both are candidates of Master of Arts (Visual Art and Design) 2010/11 as well. Their artworks explore alternative ways of communication. They investigate different approaches to fit their research concepts and methods. Therefore their artworks suggest and depict imaginative and unique perspectives of the “physical space” around them thus leading them to dialogues-making.

Figure 46: *POPaganda* series (Maizul Affendy 2010 - 2011)

Maizul’s *POPaganda* series (Maizul Affendy 2010 - 2011) invites audiences to experience a different way of cognition. Instead of reading texts to gain knowledge, Maizul suggests to the audience to read illustrations. He converts verbal communication into illustrative story-telling touching on local political issues. Through diligent news-clipping experiences, Maizul is able to express his commentary of political happenings that surround

us. He learns from the collecting experience so in theory he responds to Concrete Experiences (CE) according to the LSI.

Figure 47: *Between Utopia & A Very Hard Place* (Leila 2010 - 2011)

Leila's *Between Utopia & A Very Hard Place* (Leila 2010 - 2011) reflects her adaptation to the new life of a historical city which is surrounded by greeneries and natural environment. She improvises figure-like trees to convey her thoughts and expressions, adding self-constructed objects to particular trees. Leila's works reflect rebellious behaviour. Although her work has been removed many times by the university authority but she aggressively re-installs them. Her reaction responds to Active Experiment (AE).

Maizul and Leila plans and create stimulations of their thought via art making; Maizul illustrates his view of propaganda, and Leila manifests issues about ecological utopia. They employed vivid and straightforward icons to reconstruct their narratives and subtexts; as an

effort to invoke the audience. As the result, they are constructing sets of “realities” to campaign their thought through visual tension. (The text that you are reading is also another “humanly constructed reality”)

One might ask, “What if the audiences have other interpretations?”

6.2.3 Section 3: *Dialogue In Sublimity*

Going beyond the micro/macro level reading of diagrammatic data, the thinking of an artist (or the visual interpreter) can be unveiled. It can be referred to as a set of information about the experiences of viewing, interaction, perception and “human-independent-reality” by the audience. Our experiences are unique, even looking at a same object from the same direction and distance, or tasting the same cup of beverage. Therefore the 1st person’s experiences cannot be compared to the 2nd person’s, so instead of sharing the experiences, it is better to gain one’s own.

Section 3 includes installations by Nuzul Haqimi and Ting Chuang, a collaboration that shares their discovery of reality with the audience through their respective experiences. According to Figure 37, Nuzul and Ting Chuang are positioned inside the smaller cube, and are located almost in the middle of the diagram. Nuzul assembled small structures into larger installations. Ting Chuang has a fetish to retouch his antique and collectable items. They work hand-in-hand to express their past experiences through repeatability of making (habits), subconsciously unveiling the manifestation of their subliminal reaction. The result of the collaboration can be referred to as a simulation of experience-sharing. On the other hand, their works are conscious strategies to invite audiences to participate.

Table 8: Summary of micro level diagrammatic data. (Kolb 1984, 2011) (Zull 2002) (Hasnul Jamal Saidon, Liew Ting Chuang 2008 - ?)

Nuzul constructs overhead hanging structures with random drop strings, entitled *Your Tactile Perception* (Nuzul Haqimi 2011) that is defined as an environment for audiences to interact. The structures invoke the audiences' reactions – the sense of being an object moving inside the space; either they are touching or avoiding objects in the setting based on the audiences' tactile perception. Nuzul's "setting" gives different experiences to his audiences.

Figure 48: *Your Tactile Perception* (Nuzul Haqimi 2011)

Ting Chuang's *The Returning – Silent Dialogue* (Ting Chuang 2010-2011), also entitled *White-wooden-chair* (WWC) invites the public to capture candid photographs then upload them to *Facebook.com* for further interaction. A hidden camera is installed into the chair to capture the spontaneous response of the public. Then a real-time video image is projected onto a wall with a tree-like silhouette. Juxtaposition of the artificial tree shadow

and projected participants' image showcases the performance between White-Wooden-Chair and the participants, highlighting its "performative" quality. (Wikipedia 2011)

Nuzul and Ting Chuang's modular installations re-construct the given space into an exciting shadow playground. This thematically and conceptually discusses the notion of reality in the physical and virtual world; through the intersection of silhouettes, cast shadows, reflected shadows, projected silhouettes and cut-out silhouettes. *Shadow Playground* (Hasnul Jamal, Ting Chuang and Nuzul Haqimi 1997, 2008, 2011) portrays the interaction of different type of shadows as well. Audiences are exposed to realize the existence of humanly constructed reality and human-independent reality to understand its significance. (Rusbult 2003)

Shadow Playground, an integration video installation which is adopted from Hasnul and Ting Chuang's in collaboration stop motion video entitled, *Post-fictional Dialogue* (Hasnul Jamal and Ting Chuang, Post-Fictional Dialogue 1997, 2008) and Nuzul's cut-boxes modular installation.

Figure 49: *Shadow Playground* (Hasnul Jamal, Ting Chuang and Nuzul Haqimi, *Shadow Playground* 1997, 2008, 2011)

One might ask, “What if the audience does not enjoying the shadow playground?”

6.2.4 Theme for the exhibition: *Silent Dialogue – “Semicolon-close parenthesis”*

1. “You see what you want to see.” It’s true that artworks say many things to different people, and even art historians do not agree completely about everything. Quoted from Charles R. Jansen, *Studying Art History* (Jensen 1986)
2. Particles and waves are merely mathematical tools. Light is whatever light is; not a particle and it is not a wave. I would like to say that light is light and these texts aren’t texts – there are merely some lines on a piece of paper. Quoted from Travis Taylor, *The Science Behind The Secret* (Taylor 2010)

3. Diagrammatic data; the reader gets a general impression of what is being communicated, then on closer inspection engages in more detailed matters. Quoted from Carolyn Knight, Jessica Glaser *Diagrams – Innovative Solutions for Graphic Designers* (Carolyn Knight, Jessica Glaser 2009)
4. The main message is that learning is change. It is change in us, because it is change in the brain. Thus the art of teaching must be the art of changing the brain. Quoted from James E. Zull, *The Art of Changing the Brain* (Zull 2002)
5. A failure to make this distinction, or a stubborn refusal to make it, will cause confusion. Therefore, if we want our thinking to be more precise and less confused, we will always ask "Which type of reality is it?" Quoted from Craig Rusbult, *Reality 101* (Rusbult 2003)
6. God sleeps in the rock, dreams in the plant, stirs in the animal and awakens in mankind. (Sufi teaching) (Hasnul Jamal, Takung 2006)
7. There was an entity, out of the chaos, perfect, before Heaven and Earth were born. Silent, alas, void, alas, self-contained, unchangeable, acting everywhere, yet inexhaustible: it may be therefore regarded as all world's primal mother. (Lao Zi, Tao Te Ching, Chapter 25) (陈鼓应 2003)

This exhibition is seeking for intertextuality through dialogues within the exhibits – the “silent dialogues” in the dimension that surrounds us.

One might ask, “What is the actual dialogue that is being communicated through the exhibition?”

My answer is, simply “semicolon-close parenthesis” because while you are viewing the exhibits; you are making a “silent dialogues”. Again, *Silent Dialogue – “Semicolon-close parenthesis” ;)*

(Written in May 2011)

6.3 *White-wooden-chair* actualises the “quantum leap”.

In physic and chemistry, quantum leap is a change of one electron from one quantum state to another within an atom, this phenomenal refers as atomic electron transition as well. In another words, quantum leap is the process of negative cache atom neutralise into positive cache; where the extra electron “jumped” from one to another atom. (Wikipedia, Atomic electron transition 2011) In our daily life, “quantum leap” describes the transition of life on surface meaning. Deeper interpretation of “quantum leap” is refers to the completion of a cycle of moment and life; or the law of circulation (循环运动) in Daoism. (陈鼓应 2003)

This section excerpted the short synopsis of *The Making Archive II - Process Exhibition, Showcase of MA (Visual Art & Design) Studio Research Outcome 2011* which exhibited at Gallery *Dua Puluh Tujuh*, Universiti Sains Malaysia.

Artists are seeking for new mediums, exploiting cutting edge technology in order to widen the possibility of expression and creation of marks. (Fauzan 2007) In tandem with such imperative the M.A. (Visual Arts & Design) curriculum requires each student to identify and investigate his/her own approach to art making. Everyone works independently, selecting the genre, medium, techniques, style or working strategy, model and presentation that fit his/her research concepts and methods. On the other hand, certain patterns of art making can be traced through the process of studio practices, by examining the setting, working behaviour, mark-makings, presented ideas, conceptual mappings, experimented results and any other activities that take place in the studio. As a platform for the artist to practice his/her methodological preferences, the studio thus functions as a site laden with behaviourist data. The artist studio resembles a scientific laboratory in which experiments are conducted and theories are contextualised.

Figure 50: The Making Archive II - Process Exhibition 2011 at Gallery *Dua Puluh Tujuh*.

The showcase exhibited research materials, studies, scribbles and sketches, concept map, notes and documentation photographs of the making. It is for searching the meaning of returning (refers to returning of hometown), exploring the experience of transition, experiencing the engagement, realising the consciousness, making the refinement, observing the experiment and returning to the “departure point” of the very basic intention. In other words the endeavour in *White-wooden-chair* project demonstrates the proposed “Cycle of Art Making” (in my terminology, Cycle of Interaction/Experience) which is based on the proposed “Defragmentation the ‘Big Apple’ argument” – compression of theoretical frameworks. Further it is leading to the phenomenal of “The Returning” to “Meeting the South”.

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Chapter 7: White-wooden-chair is revolving from “The returning” to “Meeting the South” (Creation)

(This chapter is the reflection of the endeavour in this Master of Arts (Visual Art & Design) project. Partly it is harvesting the fruit of my effort; completed the Chinese saying, 种瓜得瓜, 种豆得豆。明·施耐庵《水浒传》第四十五回 [if a man plants melons he will reap melons; if he sows beans, he will reap beans])

Kak Ida (Mdm. Faridah Hashim, the pioneering staff of Muzium & Galeri Tuanku Fauziah, USM) commented, the tree-silhouette is metaphor for the transformation of USM Museum & Gallery to (present) Muzium & Gallery Tuanku Fauziah; where those pioneer contributors and artists namely T. K. Sabapathy, late Redza Piyadasa, Ismail Hashim, Dr. Chew Teng Beng, Robert C. Crock, Dr. Zakaria Ali and others have sowed the “seeds” on this beautiful land in Penang Island since the early 1970’s, like the antique chair grown root on its leg, and upward it has grown branches and leaves; White-wooden-chair has actualised Kak Ida and many contributors’ dreams as well. Kak Ida’s comment is the most sincere comment which is more important than any others rewards. Her comment has touched my heart and soul, very much.

The beautiful comment concludes my discoveries and adventures as I have mentioned at *Chapter 1*. Kak Ida has faithfully perceived the interaction/experience that *White-wooden-chair* has offered. Kak Ida’s reaction is the signifier to enlighten my life is “never empty”. Her description has answered my doubt of the existence of me – the “half growing fruit” (being); truly realise the important of cycle of life, where Chapter 7 is the end of this thesis; but it is the beginning of my journey toward the south, toward the participation of Signature Art Prize 2011. As I phrase as, *White-wooden-chair* is in “The Returning” to “Meeting the South”.

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